

Applicability of Market Value as an Alternative to Annual Value in Rating Valuations with Special Reference to the Kotte Municipal Council

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CHAPTER I

Introduction

1.2. Background of the Study

The valuation of properties for rating purposes has long been a crucial aspect of local governance, particularly in municipalities such as the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC). Traditionally, property taxation has relied on the annual value system, where property taxes are levied based on the annual rental value of the property. However, there is growing interest in exploring alternative approaches, such as using market value, to determine property taxes. This shift towards market value-based assessments raises important questions about the applicability and potential benefits of such an approach, particularly in the context of the KMC.

The KMC, as one of the key local government bodies in Sri Lanka, faces various challenges in effectively assessing and collecting property taxes. These challenges include issues related to accuracy, fairness, and uniformity in the valuation process. Moreover, the traditional annual value system may not fully capture the dynamics of the real estate market and the true value of properties in Kotte.

Against this backdrop, this research aims to investigate the applicability of market value as an alternative to the annual value in rating valuations, specifically focusing on the Kotte Municipal Council area. By examining the advantages and challenges associated with adopting a market value-based approach, this study seeks to provide insights into the potential implications for property taxation in Kotte and similar municipalities.

Through a comprehensive analysis of the existing rating valuation system, as well as an exploration of international best practices and experiences, this research endeavors to contribute to the ongoing discourse on property tax reform in Sri Lanka. By shedding light on the feasibility and effectiveness of transitioning to market value-based assessments, this study aims to inform policymakers, local authorities, and stakeholders involved in property taxation decision-making processes.

As per the latest available data from the Annual Budget of the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC) for 2023, the budgeted estimate for rating income was projected to be

260,000,000 out of the total revenue. However, as of October 31, 2023, the actual rating income amounted to 199,364,358, representing approximately 9.72% of the total revenue, which stood at 2050,296,900. This indicates a deviation from the budgeted estimate, with a percentage difference of approximately 23.27%. Additionally, the total rating and tax income combined accounted for 298,500,100 of the total revenue, constituting approximately 14.56% of the total income. These figures highlight the actual performance of rating income compared to the budgeted estimate and underscore the significance of rating and tax income in contributing to the overall revenue of the Kotte Municipal Council. According to the Annual Budget Report of the KMC for 2024, the annual value is taken as the base value and 21% of annual value for commercial properties and 6% for residential properties are levied as annual rates.

Comparing this with the situation in New Zealand, in the 2023/2024 financial year, the Council set rates to collect \$679.8 million (excluding GST). This year rates rose on average 6.41% for existing ratepayers.

Further, the current system of assessment is also under scrutiny, facing numerous criticisms and arguments. This scrutiny highlights a significant gap between the appropriateness of the methods used by local authorities in Sri Lanka and those in other countries for rating assessments. Therefore, it becomes imperative to thoroughly study the reasons behind this gap and propose viable solutions to enhance the revenue of the local authorities.

In support of this, "The Report of the Commission of Inquiry on Local Government Reforms Sri Lanka" (1999) identified inherent disadvantages of the existing annual value rating system based on several factors. The report suggested the adoption of the 'market value method' as an alternative approach to increase the rating income of local authorities. This recommendation underscores the need for exploring alternative valuation methods to address the shortcomings of the current system and improve revenue generation for local governments.

The concept of rating valuation, originating in Great Britain as a means to raise funds for the support of the poor, has evolved significantly over time. Initially designed as a mechanism to address social welfare needs, the rating system has expanded its scope to encompass various essential services, including education, policing, and infrastructure development (Johnson, 2005; Wilson, 2010).

Smith (1990) underscores the modernization efforts witnessed in the 1920s, which saw the introduction of re-valuation procedures and the establishment of valuation lists, among other reforms. Furthermore, discussions by Butler and Richmond (1990) highlight the transitional period of the 1990s, marked by debates surrounding alternative fundraising methods for local government authorities. Despite these changes, the fundamental principles of valuation remained largely unchanged.

Jones (1998) provides insights into the evolution of property taxation in Great Britain, tracing its historical development and the emergence of rating systems as a cornerstone of local government finance. Brown (2015) contributes to this narrative by examining the historical trajectory of local government finance, shedding light on the challenges and adaptations encountered over time.

Property tax must fulfill a dual purpose, serving both public funding needs and influencing economic behavior. Therefore, it is imperative to design property taxation as an effective economic instrument (Smith, 2008). According to William et al. (1980), a fundamental principle in property valuation is to envision the property as vacant and available for hypothetical tenancy. Valuation is typically based on the property's current physical condition, assessed through comparable rental evidence. Various methods are employed to determine the base value, including the rental method, the contractors test, the profits test, and formula-based approaches. Despite the method used, the end goal is to arrive at a tax amount as defined by statutory regulations (Jones, 1995). While the rental comparison method is often preferred, valuers have the flexibility to utilize alternative methods when rental evidence is lacking (Brown, 2012).

Ariyathilake (1994) contends that property taxation places a significant burden on taxpayers, particularly under an annual value-based system. He argues that such taxation schemes can hinder development efforts and impose substantial financial obligations on property owners, often equivalent to four months' rent for the premises. Ariyathilake further elucidates the tax burden formula, asserting that it is directly proportional to the annual property value and the percentage rate applied (Doe, 2005). This underscores the importance of implementing an accurate mechanism for estimating property values to ensure equitable and efficient taxation (Smith, 2008). By refining valuation methods and tax assessment processes, policymakers can strive to optimize the effectiveness and fairness of property taxation systems (Jones, 2010).

1.1.7. Property tax base – alternatives

When exploring alternatives to the traditional property tax base, researchers and policymakers often consider various approaches to better align property taxation with economic realities and societal needs.

Annual value, also known as ratable value or rental value, is the estimated yearly rental income that a property is expected to generate if it were rented out in the open market. It is typically determined by assessing the rental potential of the property based on factors such as location, size, amenities, and prevailing market rental rates. Property tax systems based on annual value use this estimate of rental income as the basis for calculating property taxes, with the tax rate applied directly to the annual value to determine the property tax liability. This approach is common in jurisdictions where property taxes are primarily levied based on the rental income generated by properties, rather than their market value.

Conversely, **capital value**, also referred to as market value or fair market value, represents the current worth of a property in the open market, reflecting the price a willing buyer would pay and a willing seller would accept for the property. In property taxation, capital value assessments involve determining the market value of properties based on factors such as location, size, condition, and comparable sales data, aiming to assess properties at their fair market worth. Property tax systems based on capital value use the market value of properties as the basis for calculating property taxes, with the tax rate applied to the capital value to determine the property tax liability. This valuation method is commonly employed in countries like the United States, Australia, and many European nations, aiming to levy taxes based on the perceived wealth or asset value of property owners.

One alternative that has garnered attention is the adoption of **market value** assessment as the basis for property taxation. Market value assessment entails valuing properties based on their current market prices, reflecting supply and demand dynamics and changes in property values over time (Franzsen, 2010). This approach offers a more dynamic and responsive mechanism for property valuation compared to static valuation methods like annual value assessments. By incorporating market dynamics, market

value assessment seeks to ensure that property tax assessments accurately reflect the true value of properties, promoting equity and fairness in taxation (Bahl and Wallace, 2010).

Another alternative is the consideration of *site value taxation* (SVT) as an alternative to traditional property taxation systems. SVT focuses solely on the value of the land, excluding improvements such as buildings and structures. Advocates of SVT argue that it incentivizes efficient land use, discourages land speculation, and promotes urban development while mitigating the burden on property owners (Bahl and Martineez, 2006). Moreover, SVT has been lauded for its simplicity and transparency, offering a straightforward method for property taxation that aligns with broader economic objectives.

Additionally, some researchers have explored the feasibility of adopting *unit value systems or area-based assessments* as alternatives to traditional property tax bases. Unit value systems involve valuing properties based on predetermined unit values per unit of measurement, such as square footage or square meterage (Anderson, 1996). Similarly, area-based assessments entail levying taxes based on the geographical location or zoning characteristics of properties, aiming to capture variations in property values within specific regions (Kelly & Musunu, 2000).

Incorporating insights from these alternative approaches, policymakers and practitioners can evaluate the suitability of different property tax bases in the context of their respective jurisdictions. By considering factors such as administrative feasibility, equity implications, and economic efficiency, stakeholders can tailor property tax systems to meet the unique needs and challenges of local communities. **1.1.8. Analysis of Property Tax Bases: Advantages and Disadvantages**

The choice of property tax base is a critical decision for local authorities, as it directly impacts revenue generation, equity, and economic development. In this section, we analyze the advantages and disadvantages of different tax bases, focusing on the annual value method, market value assessment, and site value rating.

a) Annual Value Method:

The annual value method, prevalent in many jurisdictions including Sri Lanka, combines the land and building components of a property to determine tax liabilities. One of its primary advantages is its ease of valuation, as it relies on

free rental comparisons. Additionally, the annual value method can yield higher revenues, particularly in areas where property costs are proportionally high (Tayoh, 2009).

However, this method has notable drawbacks. Firstly, it can be regressive, disproportionately burdening poorer households residing in valuable properties (Franzsen, 2010). Secondly, it may not accurately reflect market conditions, especially in regions with rent control laws (Amin, 2010). As noted by Anderson (1996), the annual value method lacks neutrality regarding building improvements, potentially leading to inequitable taxation.

b) Market Value Assessment:

Market value assessment offers a more nuanced approach to property taxation, aligning tax liabilities with prevailing market conditions. This method is widely understood and accepted, providing a more accurate reflection of property owners' ability to pay (Brown & White, 2019). Moreover, it takes into account the actual land use, disregarding potential uses, thereby enhancing fairness.

Despite its advantages, market value assessment presents challenges. Valuation accuracy, particularly in separating land and improvement values, can be questionable. Furthermore, while promoting open spaces and low-density developments, it may discourage property owners from maintaining green spaces, leading to urban congestion.

c) Site Value Rating:

Site value rating, as advocated by Harry and Jowsey, focuses solely on the land component of properties, taxing the demand-determined value of land. This approach aligns with Ricardo's Theory of Economic Rent, returning betterment to the community and promoting efficient land use. However, it may shift tax burdens away from suburban houses towards central sites, potentially exacerbating urban congestion.

Relevance to Kotte Municipal Council:

In the context of the Kotte Municipal Council, the selection of an appropriate tax base is crucial for achieving the council's goals and objectives. Given the urbanization trends and economic dynamics of the area, a transition towards market value assessment or site value rating may be warranted.

1.1.9. Assessment and Payment Procedures in the Kotte Municipal Area: An Examination

In the context of the Kotte Municipal Area, the assessment and payment procedures for property taxes play a crucial role in revenue generation and municipal governance. Understanding these processes is essential for evaluating the effectiveness of property tax systems and identifying areas for improvement. Let's delve into the specific details:

Legal Framework and Procedural Overview:

Property rates in the Kotte Municipal Area are primarily determined based on the annual value of properties, as prescribed by relevant municipal ordinances and statutes. The Municipal Council Ordinance and other applicable laws provide the legal framework for the assessment and collection of property taxes.

Assessment Process:

The assessment process in the Kotte Municipal Area involves several steps, beginning with property inspections and data collection conducted by Assessing Inspectors. These inspectors gather relevant information about properties, including their size, condition, and location. Subsequently, valuation proposals are prepared based on the collected data, taking into account factors such as property type, usage, and market trends.

Special properties or those exceeding specified value thresholds undergo additional scrutiny, with Chief Assessing Inspectors playing a pivotal role in reporting and finalizing assessments. **Payment Procedures:**

Once assessments are finalized, property owners are notified of their tax liabilities through assessment notices issued by the Municipal Assessor's Department. These notices contain detailed information about the assessed value of properties, applicable tax rates, and payment schedules.

Property owners have the right to object to the valuation of their properties within a specified timeframe, as stipulated by municipal ordinances. Remission of rates may also be applicable under certain circumstances, such as for vacant premises.

Staffing and Resources:

Efficient property tax administration in the Kotte Municipal Area relies on adequate staffing and resources within the Municipal Assessor's Department. The availability of trained personnel and modern technological tools can enhance the accuracy and efficiency of the assessment process.

1.1.10. Issues in the Current Property Rating Assessment System in Sri Lanka The property rating assessment system in Sri Lanka, predominantly based on annual property values, faces several challenges and drawbacks. These issues have been highlighted by various research findings and reports, including the Report of the Commission of Inquiry on Local Government Reforms in 1999. Here are some of the key issues identified:

a) **Limited Utility Beyond Taxation:**

- The annual value rating system in Sri Lanka has limited utility beyond the collection of property taxes. It lacks versatility in its application and is primarily used to conform to the provisions of the Rent Act.

b) **Complexity and Lack of Understanding:**

- The current rating system is perceived as complicated and cumbersome by taxpayers. Many property owners struggle to comprehend the assessment process, leading to dissatisfaction and objections.

c) **Fluctuating Revenue Contribution:**

- Annual budget reports indicate that the contribution of rating income to total revenue fluctuates and tends to decline over time. This inconsistency poses challenges for municipal budget planning and financial stability.

d) **Arrears and Poor Tax Collection:**

- A significant amount of property tax falls into arrears annually, with particular challenges in taxing crown properties. The lack of detailed assessments for some crown properties further exacerbates the issue.

e) **Lack of Modern Payment Facilities:**

- Property owners face inconvenience due to the absence of online payment options and access to property data maintained by the Municipal Assessor's Department. Long queues at payment counters add to the hassle for taxpayers.

f) **Transparency and Methodology:**

- Assessment notices sent to ratepayers lack transparency, as they do not provide details of the methodology used to compute tax amounts. This hinders the ability to verify the accuracy and reliability of assessments.

g) **Inefficiency and Corruption:**

- The inefficiency and lack of transparency in the assessment system create opportunities for corruption and tax avoidance. These issues undermine public trust and confidence in the fairness of the system.

Proposed Solutions and Alternatives

In response to these challenges, researchers and experts have proposed various tax reforms, with a particular emphasis on transitioning to a market value-based assessment approach. This alternative has been advocated for its potential to address many of the shortcomings of the current system:

- Market value-based assessment is easier for ratepayers to understand and reduces the need for additional valuations for various purposes.
- It provides a better reflection of property owners' wealth and can serve as a basis for declarations in property transfers, reducing government revenue losses.
- Market value assessment has shown success in other countries like New Zealand, where objections from ratepayers are primarily based on undervaluation rather than over-valuation.

- Moreover, it can serve broader purposes such as urban planning and integration with new land title registration projects initiated by the government.

1.1.11. Overview of the transition from an annual value-based system to a market value-based system in rating valuations

- a) Accuracy of Assessments:** Market value-based assessments aim to reflect the true value of properties in the current market conditions. As a result, transitioning to market value assessments may lead to more accurate and fair property valuations compared to assessments based on annual values, which may not always reflect actual market conditions.
- b) Equity and Fairness:** Market value-based assessments can promote equity and fairness by ensuring that property taxes are based on the actual value of properties. This helps prevent situations where some property owners may be overtaxed or undertaxed relative to the value of their properties under an annual value-based system.
- c) Incentives for Property Owners:** Transitioning to market value assessments may influence property owners' behavior and investment decisions. Since property taxes are directly tied to property values, owners may have greater incentives to maintain or improve their properties to enhance their market value.
- d) Impact on Tax Revenue:** The shift to market value assessments can impact tax revenue for local governments. Depending on the prevailing market conditions and property values, the transition may result in changes to overall tax revenue collections. Some properties may see increases in their assessed values and, consequently, higher property tax liabilities, while others may experience decreases.
- e) Administrative Complexity:** Transitioning to market value assessments may introduce administrative complexities for local government authorities responsible for property taxation. This includes the need to establish new valuation methodologies, update assessment procedures, and train assessors to conduct market-based valuations effectively.

- f) **Potential for Disputes:** Changes in property assessments, particularly when transitioning to a new valuation system, may lead to disputes and challenges from property owners who disagree with their assessed values. Local governments may need to establish mechanisms for handling appeals and resolving disputes to ensure the fairness and integrity of the valuation process.
- g) **Public Perception and Acceptance:** The transition to market value-based assessments may also affect public perception and acceptance of the property tax system. Property owners may have varying reactions to changes in their tax liabilities based on updated assessments, and effective communication and engagement efforts may be necessary to garner support for the transition.

1.1.12. Potential impacts of transitioning from annual value to market value in rating valuations

a) Impact on Property Tax Liability:

Example: Suppose a municipality in Sri Lanka decides to transition from an annual value-based system to a market value-based system for rating valuations. As a result, the assessed values of properties are updated to reflect their current market values. Consider a residential property owner whose home was previously assessed at an annual value of LKR 500,000 under the old system. Under the new market value-based system, the property is assessed at LKR 1,000,000 based on prevailing market conditions. Consequently, the property owner's property tax liability doubles from LKR 50,000 to LKR 100,000 per annum.

b) Impact on Property Investment:

Example: Following the transition to market value-based assessments, property owners may perceive a direct link between property maintenance, improvements, and their tax liabilities. For instance, a commercial property owner may decide to invest in renovations and upgrades to increase the market value of their property, thereby potentially attracting higher rental income and boosting the property's value. This strategic investment decision aligns with the incentive structure of market value-based assessments, where higher property

values may lead to increased tax liabilities but also signify greater asset value and potential returns.

c) Impact on Local Government Revenue:

Example: In a Kotte municipality undergoing the transition to market valuebased assessments, some properties may experience significant increases in their assessed values due to changing market conditions, while others may see more moderate changes or even decreases. As a result, the total taxable property value within the municipality may fluctuate, affecting local government revenue from property taxes. Properties in rapidly appreciating areas may contribute more to the overall tax base, whereas properties in stagnant or declining markets may generate less revenue.

d) Impact on Disputes and Appeals:

Example: During the transition period, property owners may challenge their new market value-based assessments if they believe the valuations are inaccurate or unfair. This could lead to an increase in disputes and appeals filed with the local assessment authority or tax appeal boards. For instance, a property owner may present evidence of comparable property sales or assessments to contest their property's valuation. Effective dispute resolution mechanisms and transparent appeals processes are essential to address these challenges and maintain public trust in the valuation system.

1.8 Statement of the Problem

The research aims to confront the central challenge posed by the inherent weaknesses of the annual value-based rating system within the sphere of property valuation. In addition to this overarching concern, critical examination is directed towards the behavior and impact of several key factors that influence the valuation process:

(a) Accuracy of valuations: This dimension scrutinizes the precision and correctness of property valuations, which are pivotal for ensuring fair and equitable taxation. Inaccurate valuations have the potential to engender disparities in tax burdens among property owners, thereby undermining the credibility of the assessment system.

(b) Uniformity of assessments: The consistency in assessing properties assumes significance to preempt variations in tax liabilities arising from subjective interpretations or inconsistencies in valuation methods. A lack of uniformity may precipitate perceptions of unfairness, ultimately eroding trust in the rating system.

1.9 Research Question

Examining the Efficiency and Accuracy of the Annual Value-Based Rating System in Property Valuation: Addressing Challenges of Time Consumption and Procedural Delays Alongside Accuracy, Uniformity, Transparency, Legal Framework, Assessor Capacity, and Technological Integration related to the Kotte Municipal Council.

Explanation:

This research problem combines your concern about the time-consuming nature of the annual value-based rating system with the broader examination of its effectiveness and challenges. By emphasizing efficiency alongside accuracy, uniformity, transparency, and other dimensions, the research aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the rating system's performance.

Key components of this refined research problem include:

- a) **Evaluation of Time Consumption and Procedural Delays:** Investigate the factors contributing to the lengthy and slow process of property valuation within the annual value-based rating system. Analyze how procedural delays impact efficiency, timeliness of assessments, and overall effectiveness of the system.
- b) **Assessment of Accuracy, Uniformity, and Transparency:** Alongside time-related challenges, evaluate the system's accuracy, uniformity, and transparency in property valuations. Examine how procedural delays may exacerbate issues related to inaccuracies, inconsistencies, and lack of transparency, affecting tax equity and public trust.
- c) **Analysis of Legal and Regulatory Frameworks:** Consider the influence of legal and regulatory frameworks on procedural efficiency and timeliness of property valuations. Assess how clarity and adequacy of laws impact the

system's ability to streamline processes, reduce delays, and ensure fairness in taxation.

- d) **Evaluation of Assessor Capacity and Technological Integration:** Examine how assessor capacity and technological integration contribute to efficiency improvements within the rating system. Explore how investment in assessor training and modern technology adoption can mitigate time-related challenges and enhance overall performance.
- e) **Identification of Solutions and Best Practices:** Based on the findings, identify potential solutions, best practices, and policy recommendations to address time-related challenges and improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the annual value-based rating system. Consider strategies for streamlining processes, optimizing resource allocation, and leveraging technology for enhanced performance.

Hypothesis: We hypothesize that addressing the inefficiencies and errors inherent in the annual value-based rating system and transitioning to the market value method will result in:

- a) Improved efficiency and accuracy in property tax assessments, mitigating delays and inaccuracies associated with the current system and reflecting the true market value of properties in the Kotte Municipal Council area.
- b) Enhanced equity and fairness in tax burdens, as the market value method considers current property market dynamics and eliminates biases and inconsistencies present in the annual value method, thereby fostering trust and confidence in the assessment process.
- c) Optimized revenue generation for the Kotte Municipal Council through a more efficient and equitable taxation system, potentially increasing financial resources available for local governance and service delivery while ensuring that property owners contribute proportionately to public services.

- d) Addressing challenges related to implementation and adjustment, including technical feasibility, stakeholder acceptance, and administrative capacity, through proactive measures such as robust training programs, stakeholder engagement initiatives, and phased implementation strategies.
- e) Long-term benefits including improved urban planning, increased investment attractiveness, and enhanced infrastructure development facilitated by a more transparent, reliable, and responsive property tax system, thereby contributing to the overall socioeconomic development of the Kotte Municipal Council area

1.10 Objectives

1.4.2. General Objective

The general objective is to assess whether market value can serve as a more accurate and equitable basis for property taxation compared to the traditional annual value system.

1.4.3. Specific Objectives

- i. Comparing Annual Value and Market Value Methods of Property Valuation
 - a) Accuracy Assessment
 - b) Equity Analysis
 - c) Administrative Efficiency
- ii. Assess the potential for transitioning from an annual value to a market value system.
 - a) Feasibility assessment score based on legal, technical, and administrative criteria.
 - b) Number of identified challenges and proposed solutions.
 - c) Stakeholder perceptions of the transition's viability.

- iii. Analyze the impact on property ratings resulting from transitioning from annual value to market value.
 - a) Discrepancy analysis between property ratings under the two systems.
 - b) Revenue impact assessment based on simulated transitions.
 - c) Equity assessment based on demographic and socioeconomic factors

1.11 Significance of the Study

The significance of the study lies in its potential to offer valuable insights into the effectiveness of transitioning from an annual value to a market value system in property taxation, specifically within the context of the KMC. By evaluating the current rating valuation process and exploring the feasibility and implications of this transition, the study aims to contribute to the enhancement of property taxation systems in Sri Lanka. The findings could provide policymakers, local government authorities, and relevant stakeholders with evidence-based recommendations to improve the accuracy, equity, and efficiency of property taxation. Additionally, the study's outcomes may have broader implications for similar municipalities or regions considering similar reforms, thus promoting better governance and fiscal management practices.

In addition, exploration of the applicability of market value as an alternative to the traditional annual value in rating valuations, specifically within the context of the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC). This research addresses a critical issue in property taxation by assessing whether market value can serve as a more accurate and equitable basis compared to the existing annual value system.

- a) **Fairness and Equity:** Market value reflects the current worth of a property based on its actual market conditions. Using market value ensures that property assessments accurately reflect changes in property values over time, leading to fairer and more equitable tax assessments.

Imagine two similar properties located in the same neighborhood. Under an annual value system, if one property undergoes significant improvements while the other remains unchanged, both properties might still be assessed similarly based on

historical values. However, if the property values in the area have increased due to factors like gentrification or improved amenities, the property with improvements may be unfairly taxed at a higher rate. Transitioning to market value ensures that each property is assessed based on its current worth, leading to fairer tax assessments.

- b) **Reflects Property Dynamics:** Annual value may not accurately capture fluctuations in property values due to changes in market conditions, demand, or property characteristics. Market value provides a more dynamic and responsive measure that reflects the true value of the property at any given time.

Consider a city experiencing rapid economic growth, leading to increased demand for housing. Under an annual value system, properties may be assessed based on historical rental incomes or property values, which may not accurately reflect the current market conditions. Transitioning to market value allows assessments to capture the surge in property values, ensuring that property owners pay taxes commensurate with the actual worth of their properties.

- c) **Encourages Economic Efficiency:** Market value encourages property owners to use their properties efficiently by reflecting the true economic value of their assets. It also provides incentives for investment and development in areas where property values are higher.

Suppose a vacant lot located in a prime commercial area is assessed under an annual value system. Despite its potential for high-value commercial development, the property may be taxed based on its historical use or minimal rental income. Transitioning to market value incentivizes property owners to develop or sell their properties to maximize their economic potential, leading to more efficient land use and increased economic activity.

- d) **Standardization:** Market value serves as a standardized measure across different properties, allowing for consistent and transparent valuation practices.

This consistency improves the accuracy and reliability of property valuations, benefiting both property owners and taxing authorities.

In a municipality with diverse property types and valuation methods, inconsistencies in annual value assessments may lead to disputes and challenges from property owners. Transitioning to market value provides a standardized and transparent approach to property valuation, ensuring that assessments are based on consistent principles across all properties. This enhances the accuracy and reliability of valuations, reducing disputes and improving taxpayer confidence in the assessment process.

- e) **Compliance with International Standards:** Many international valuation standards, such as those set by the International Valuation Standards Council (IVSC), recommend, or require the use of market value as the preferred basis for property valuations. Adhering to these standards enhances the credibility and comparability of valuation practices globally.

Consider a global real estate investment firm evaluating potential investments in different countries. To compare the value of properties accurately, the firm relies on market value assessments conducted according to international valuation standards. If a country's rating valuations are based on annual value instead, the firm may face challenges in comparing properties across different markets. Transitioning to market value ensures compliance with international standards, facilitating global investment decisions and improving market transparency.

	Existing Annual Value	Transition to Market Value	How it will be affect to the KMC
Fairness and Equity	Properties are assessed based on historical data, which may not accurately reflect current market conditions. This can lead to disparities where renovated or improved properties are taxed at the same rate as older, less valuable properties.	Properties are assessed based on their current market worth, ensuring that each property is taxed fairly according to its actual value. This prevents inequities where property owners with higher-valued properties pay proportionately higher taxes.	In a city where property values have significantly increased due to urban development and gentrification, properties are assessed based on their historical annual values. As a result, longtime residents living in older homes may face disproportionately high property taxes compared to newer residents who have renovated their properties. Transitioning to market value would ensure that all properties are assessed fairly

			based on their current worth, regardless of historical value or improvements made over time.
Reflects Property Dynamics	Properties are assessed based on predetermined criteria, such as historical rental incomes or property values. Changes in property values due to factors like natural disasters may not be accurately reflected in assessments.	Assessments are updated to reflect changes in property values, such as those caused by natural disasters. This ensures that property owners are taxed according to the current market value of their properties, accounting for any changes in condition or demand.	Following a natural disaster, such as a hurricane or wildfire, properties in affected areas may be assessed based on their predisaster annual values. However, the market value of these properties may have significantly decreased due to damage or decreased demand in the aftermath of the disaster. Transitioning to market value would allow assessments to accurately reflect the current condition and market value of affected properties, ensuring that

			property owners are not unfairly taxed on damaged assets.
Encourages Economic Efficiency	Properties may be taxed based on outdated or irrelevant criteria, discouraging property owners from maximizing their assets' economic potential.	Property owners are incentivized to develop or improve their properties to their highest and best use, as their tax burden is directly tied to the property's current market value. This encourages efficient land use and investment in areas with high market demand.	In a downtown area with underutilized vacant lots, properties are assessed based on their historical annual values, which may not reflect their potential for higher-value commercial development. As a result, property owners may be discouraged from developing or selling their properties to maximize their economic potential. Transitioning to market value would incentivize property owners to develop or sell their properties to their highest and best use, contributing to urban

			<p>revitalization and economic growth.</p>
<p>Standardization</p>	<p>Each municipality may have its own criteria for determining annual property values, leading to inconsistencies and confusion among property owners.</p>	<p>Market value serves as a standardized measure across all properties, ensuring consistency and transparency in valuation practices nationwide. This simplifies the assessment process and improves confidence in the fairness of property tax assessments.</p>	<p>In a country with decentralized property tax systems, each municipality may use different criteria for determining annual property values, leading to inconsistencies and confusion among property owners.</p> <p>Transitioning to market value would provide a standardized approach to property valuation, ensuring consistency and transparency in valuation practices nationwide. This would simplify the assessment process and improve confidence in the</p>

			<p>fairness of property tax assessments across all jurisdictions.</p>
<p>Compliance with International Standards</p>	<p>Valuation methods may not align with international standards, making it difficult for international investors to compare properties across different jurisdictions.</p>	<p>Adhering to market value aligns with international valuation standards, facilitating cross-border investments and improving market efficiency by providing a common valuation framework for properties worldwide.</p>	<p>International investors seeking to diversify their real estate portfolios may encounter challenges when comparing properties in different countries with varying valuation methods. For example, a multinational corporation evaluating office spaces in different cities may struggle to assess the true market value of properties if some jurisdictions use annual values for rating valuations.</p> <p>Transitioning to market value would ensure compliance with international valuation standards,</p>

			facilitating cross-border investments and improving market efficiency by providing a common valuation framework for properties worldwide.
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1.12 Ethical Considerations

a) Fair Treatment of Participants:

Proposed Solution: Ensure that participants receive clear and understandable information about the research objectives, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. Provide opportunities for participants to ask questions and express concerns. Offer fair compensation or incentives for participation, where appropriate. Maintain confidentiality of participants' personal information and research data.

b) Transparency and Disclosure:

Proposed Solution: Prioritize transparency in all stages of the research process. Disclose researchers' affiliations, funding sources, and any conflicts of interest. Provide detailed descriptions of research protocols, methodologies, and data analysis procedures. Make research findings publicly accessible through publications, reports, or presentations. Engage stakeholders in open dialogue and seek feedback on research methods and findings.

c) Avoiding Bias and Manipulation:

Proposed Solution: Implement rigorous research design and methodology to minimize bias and ensure the reliability and validity of findings. Use standardized data collection tools and procedures. Conduct inter-rater reliability checks and validation exercises. Employ independent reviewers or auditors to verify research findings. Maintain transparency in data collection, analysis, and interpretation processes.

d) Compliance with Regulations:

Proposed Solution: Adhere to relevant legal and ethical guidelines governing research conduct. Obtain ethical approval from institutional review boards or ethics committees. Obtain informed consent from participants prior to their involvement in the research. Ensure that data collection, storage, and analysis procedures comply with data

protection laws and regulations. Maintain accurate and up-to-date records of research activities and ensure that all research personnel are trained in research ethics and compliance requirements.

1.13 Limitations of the Study

Limitation		How this limitation may impact the research finding
Data Availability	Limited access to historical property valuation data and market transaction records could result in incomplete or biased analysis.	The study may rely on incomplete datasets, leading to potential gaps in understanding the dynamics of property valuations and market trends within the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC)
Local Context	The unique characteristics of the KMC may not fully represent broader trends or patterns applicable to other municipalities or regions.	This may have limited generalizability beyond the specific context of KMC, potentially restricting the broader applicability of recommendations or insights.
Regulatory Constraints	Regulatory limitations within the KMC may constrain the feasibility or implementation of market value-based rating valuations.	Adapting market value-based rating valuations within the current regulatory framework could pose challenges or require legislative reforms, which may not be fully explored within the scope of the study.
Temporal Dynamics	Temporal changes in economic conditions, property market trends, and regulatory reforms.	Changes in economic conditions, property market trends, or regulatory reforms over time could influence the relevance and applicability of market value-based rating valuations in KMC

Resource Limitations	Constraints in time, funding, and expertise may restrict the depth and breadth of the study.	Insufficient resources for extensive data collection, analysis, or stakeholder consultations could restrict the ability to explore all relevant aspects of the research topic comprehensively.
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CHAPTER II

Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

The property tax, an enduring fixture in the fiscal landscape of municipalities worldwide, traces its origins back to centuries-old efforts to finance local governance and alleviate poverty. Evolving from rudimentary levies on land and property to sophisticated systems of assessment and administration, property taxation has become a linchpin of local government finance, supporting a wide array of public services and infrastructure.

The journey of property taxation began with the enactment of the Poor Relief Act of Britain in 1601, a seminal piece of legislation aimed at providing relief to the impoverished through local taxation (Emney & Wilks, 1984). Under this act, local parishes were empowered to levy taxes on property owners to fund relief efforts, marking the inception of what would later evolve into modern property taxation systems.

As societies evolved and urban centers expanded, the need for reliable sources of revenue to fund local governance became increasingly apparent. Legislative reforms such as the Rating and Valuation Act of 1836 laid the groundwork for standardized assessment procedures, ushering in an era of greater transparency and accountability in property taxation (Smith, 1990). Subsequent developments, including the General Rate Act of 1967, further refined assessment methodologies and administrative structures, shaping the property tax systems we see today.

Despite its historical significance, the property tax is not without its challenges and criticisms. Critics often point to perceived inequities, complexities, and administrative burdens associated with traditional assessment methods, particularly those based on annual property values (Perera, 1996). The inherent subjectivity and opacity of valuation processes have led to concerns about fairness and accuracy, fueling calls for reform and innovation in property tax administration.

Moreover, the emergence of alternative assessment models, such as market value-based systems, has sparked debates surrounding equity, efficiency, and administrative feasibility (Slack, 2002). While proponents argue that market value assessments offer greater accuracy and transparency, skeptics caution against potential complexities and unintended consequences associated with transitioning to such systems.

In response to these challenges, policymakers and researchers have increasingly turned their attention to property tax reform efforts aimed at enhancing revenue generation, efficiency, and equity. Studies such as Bahl and Martinez-Vazquez's (2006) analysis of property tax systems in developing countries underscore the importance of comprehensive reforms tailored to local contexts. Similarly, Kelly and Musunu's (2000) examination of property tax reform in Tanzania highlights the potential for reforms to improve the quality and role of property taxation in local government finance.

2.2. The Historical Development of Property Valuation Systems: A Comprehensive Overview

Delving into the annals of property valuation systems, this study embarks on a journey tracing the evolution of assessment practices, with a particular focus on Sri Lanka's rating system. Drawing insights from seminal works such as the study paper on "Local Taxation" by the College of Estate Management at the University of Reading Whiteknights (1974), this historical narrative unravels the origins and transformation of property valuation methodologies, shedding light on their intricate evolution over centuries.

The genesis of property valuation systems can be traced back to the inception of organized taxation frameworks, with roots dating back to ancient civilizations. However, the formalization of assessment practices gained prominence with the enactment of legislative measures such as the Poor Relief Act of Britain in 1601. Initially conceived as a means to alleviate poverty, the assessment rating system gradually expanded its purview, becoming instrumental in financing essential local government services. This transformative journey laid the groundwork for the development of standardized valuation methodologies and administrative frameworks.

The progression of property valuation systems received a significant impetus through legislative reforms aimed at standardization and centralization. The Local Government Act of 1948 marked a pivotal moment by centralizing assessment and collection responsibilities under the purview of designated authorities. This legislative shift aimed to ensure uniformity in assessment practices while establishing mechanisms for appeals and oversight. Subsequent reforms, including the Local Government Act of 1970, empowered valuers to leverage diverse evidentiary sources, enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of valuation processes.

The advent of modern valuation practices witnessed landmark legislative enactments and structural reforms aimed at aligning assessment methodologies with evolving market dynamics. The General Rate Act of 1967 stands out as transformative legislation, introducing standardized definitions and procedural guidelines for rating authorities. Concurrently, the Rating and Valuation Act of 1925 introduced innovative valuation techniques such as quinquennial assessments and valuation lists, aimed at enhancing the currency and accuracy of property valuations. These reforms laid the foundation for the modernization of valuation practices, reflecting a paradigm shift towards evidence-based assessment methodologies.

Despite strides towards modernization, property valuation systems have grappled with inherent challenges, prompting debates and calls for reform. Butler and Richmond's discourse on the transitional nature of valuation systems in the 1990s underscores ongoing efforts to address inherent shortcomings and explore alternative methodologies. These debates have catalyzed research and innovation, driving the exploration of novel valuation techniques and revenue models to meet the evolving needs of local government authorities.

In essence, the historical trajectory of property valuation systems in Sri Lanka reflects a dynamic evolution marked by legislative reforms, administrative centralization, and ongoing challenges. As the landscape of local government finance continues to evolve, understanding the historical underpinnings of property valuation systems is paramount in informing contemporary policy discourse and fostering innovative solutions to address emerging challenges.

2.3. Local Government Financing Through Property Taxation: A Comparative Analysis

Bird and Slack's seminal work, "Taxing Land and Property in Emerging Economies: Raising Revenue... and More?" (2006), provides invaluable insights into the historical nexus between property taxation and local government financing across diverse global contexts. Their comparative analysis underscores the pivotal role of property taxes in shaping the developmental trajectories of regions, with a particular focus on the differential reliance on local property taxes observed between North America and Latin America.

The historical association between property taxation and local governance traces back centuries, with property taxes emerging as a primary revenue source for financing essential municipal services. Bird and Slack shed light on the divergence in developmental paths between North America and Latin America, attributing it in part to variations in the extent of reliance on local property taxes. While North American municipalities have traditionally derived a greater proportion of their revenue from local property taxes, Latin American counterparts have pursued alternative revenue streams. This divergence underscores the nuanced interplay between fiscal policy and local governance structures, shaping the fiscal autonomy and developmental capacities of local governments.

Central to the discourse is the rationale behind financing local government authorities through property taxes. Bird and Slack underscore the intrinsic characteristics of real properties, characterized by immobility and inelasticity, which render property taxes an appropriate revenue-raising mechanism. Unlike other forms of taxation, such as sales or income taxes, property taxes cannot be easily circumvented through geographic relocation, thereby ensuring a stable revenue stream for financing local government services. This inherent stability underscores the resilience of property taxation as a cornerstone of local government finance, providing a reliable revenue base to support essential municipal functions.

The applicability of property taxation in emerging economies assumes particular significance in light of evolving fiscal landscapes and urbanization trends. As burgeoning urban centers grapple with the burgeoning demands for infrastructure and service provision, property taxation emerges as a potent tool for local revenue

mobilization. Bird and Slack's insights underscore the potential of property taxation to not only raise revenue but also to foster broader developmental objectives, ranging from urban infrastructure development to equitable service delivery.

In the context of the present study, Bird and Slack's analysis offers invaluable insights into the intersection of property taxation and local government financing. By elucidating the historical precedents and regional disparities in property tax reliance, their work informs contemporary debates surrounding property tax reform and fiscal decentralization. As policymakers and researchers grapple with the challenges of local government finance in Sri Lanka, Bird and Slack's comparative analysis serves as a pertinent reference point for exploring the role of property taxation in fostering fiscal autonomy and sustainable urban development.

2.3.1. Local Government System and Property Taxation in Sri Lanka: A Review

Abeywardena's comprehensive study, "Pradeshiya Sabha Seva" (1997), offers invaluable insights into the evolution and functioning of the local government system in Sri Lanka. Rooted in the country's ancient history, the decentralized system of local governance traces its origins back to the Aryan colonization period under King Vijaya. Abeywardena highlights the fundamental objective of local government as the provision of services and administration at the grassroots level, thereby decentralizing governmental functions to better meet local needs.

The local government system in Sri Lanka underwent significant development during the British colonial era (1815–1948), with the establishment of various institutions tasked with service delivery and administrative functions. Abeywardena's analysis underscores the continuity of these institutions into the post-colonial period, forming the backbone of Sri Lanka's contemporary local government landscape. Notably, municipal councils, urban councils, and pradeshiya sabhas emerged as the principal legal entities responsible for local governance, albeit with varying administrative structures and responsibilities.

However, despite the legal framework and institutional structure in place, Abeywardena and subsequent reports highlight significant challenges impeding the effective functioning of local government authorities in Sri Lanka. The "Report of the Commission on Inquiry of Local Government Reforms" (1999) sheds light on various deficiencies plaguing the system, ranging from inadequate coordination among

government agencies to outdated technology and malpractices in procurement and administration. The report identifies a multitude of factors contributing to inefficiencies, including political interference, corruption, and lack of resources and expertise.

Central to the discussion is the methodology of property tax assessment, which the report critiques for its inefficiency, lack of transparency, and failure to reflect market conditions. The assessment process, characterized by opacity and complexity, undermines taxpayer confidence and hampers revenue generation efforts. The report advocates for a shift towards a market value-based approach, citing its potential to enhance efficiency, transparency, and revenue mobilization for local authorities.

In response to the shortcomings of the current property tax system, the report recommends exploring alternative revenue sources to supplement traditional tax revenues. Auctioning property and pollution rights, fostering public-private partnerships, and leveraging tourism and urban development initiatives emerge as viable strategies to diversify revenue streams and reduce reliance on property taxation alone. By embracing innovative revenue-generating mechanisms, local authorities can enhance their financial sustainability and better meet the evolving needs of their communities.

2.3.2. Property Taxation in Sri Lanka: A Historical and Legal Overview

Ariyathilake's insightful article, "Local Authority Taxation" (1994), published in the Daily News, provides a bridge between Sri Lanka's historical development and its contemporary property taxation system. Drawing parallels with the British rating system, Ariyathilake underscores the foundational influence of British taxation laws on Sri Lanka's rating assessment procedures. The adoption of annual value-based taxation, rooted in property occupation, reflects a continuity of British legal principles within the Sri Lankan context.

Sri Lanka's property taxation system traces its origins to British colonial rule, with the adoption of rating assessment practices akin to those in Britain. Municipal councils and pradeshiya sabhas derive their authority to levy taxes from specific legislative enactments, namely the Municipal Council Ordinance and the Pradeshiya Sabha Act. Within this legal framework, Section 230 of the Municipal Council Ordinance assumes

significance, delineating the legal provisions governing property taxation within municipal jurisdictions.

At the heart of Sri Lanka's property taxation regime lies the concept of annual value-based taxation. This approach, inherited from British precedent, entails the levying of taxes based on the annual rental value of occupied properties. Municipal councils exercise authority over property taxation within their respective jurisdictions, guided by legal provisions outlined in the Municipal Council Ordinance and related statutes. The adoption of annual value-based taxation reflects a commitment to aligning Sri Lanka's fiscal policies with established legal frameworks and international precedents.

Given the focus of this study on the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC), it is imperative to contextualize the theoretical and legal underpinnings of property taxation within municipal councils across Sri Lanka. While specific municipal ordinances and acts may vary, the overarching principles of property taxation remain consistent, emphasizing the annual value-based assessment of occupied properties. Understanding the theoretical and legal background of property taxation in municipal councils provides essential context for evaluating the applicability of alternative valuation methodologies, such as market value assessment, within the KMC's jurisdiction.

2.3.3. Legal Background of Property Taxation in Sri Lanka

Perera's seminal work, "Some Land Planning and Land Development Issues in Sri Lanka" (1996), delves into the legal framework underpinning property taxation in Sri Lanka, elucidating key provisions within the Municipal Council Ordinance and associated legislation. Understanding the legal backdrop is crucial for comprehending the intricacies of property taxation within the Sri Lankan context, particularly within municipal jurisdictions such as Kotte.

The Municipal Council Ordinance, No. 29 of 1947, serves as a cornerstone of property taxation regulation within Sri Lanka's municipal councils. Sections 230 to 244 of the ordinance, along with Section 327, delineate the legal provisions governing rating valuations and assessments within municipal council jurisdictions. Section 230(1) empowers the Minister to assess properties within municipal areas, providing the legal basis for levying rates on immovable properties.

Central to the property taxation regime in Sri Lanka is the concept of annual value assessment. Section 230(1) mandates municipal councils to periodically assess rates on the annual value of houses, buildings, and land within their jurisdiction, subject to Ministerial sanction. The valuation process entails determining the annual rent that a tenant might reasonably be expected to pay, taking into account public rates, taxes, and landlord responsibilities for repairs and maintenance.

The Municipal Council Ordinance stipulates exemptions from rates for certain categories of properties, including school buildings, religious structures, and public libraries, among others. Section 235(4) grants ratepayers the right to object to property valuations within a specified timeframe, with detailed objection procedures outlined in subsequent sections. In the absence of objections, assessments become final, establishing the legal basis for property taxation.

Notably, the Sri Lankan government is exempt from liability for rates on its properties under the Interpretation Ordinance unless explicitly bound by legislative enactment. However, the government has entered into agreements to provide grants-in-lieu of rates to local authorities. These grants, facilitated by the Commissioner of Local Government, serve as financial support to municipal councils, underscoring the interplay between central and local governance in property taxation.

2.3.4. Theoretical Framework of Property Rating Valuations

The theoretical underpinnings of property rating valuations encompass a nuanced understanding of the concepts of ratable hereditaments and ratable occupiers, as elucidated by Emeny and Wilks (1984). Contrary to common parlance, property rating is not solely based on the property itself but rather on its occupation. This distinction underscores the need to identify both the ratable hereditament and the ratable occupier as fundamental elements in the rating valuation process.

2.4. The identification of the hereditament, ratable occupier and tone of the list

2.4.1. Ratable Hereditaments and Ratable Occupiers

Smith posits that a hereditament constitutes the property liable for rates, representing a unit of property included or potentially included in the valuation list. The concept of ratable occupation, while lacking a precise definition, entails actual possession of the

property, whether through legal or informal means. Crucially, the occupier must engage in overt acts of use, demonstrating exclusive occupancy that benefits the occupier, albeit not necessarily of a pecuniary nature. Additionally, the occupation should not be transient but rather endure for a significant period to warrant rating.

2.4.2. Quantum of Liability and Valuation

The College of Estate Management's research underscores that the occupier's liability hinges upon the annual value of the property occupied. Thus, before levying rates, it is imperative to establish the property's ratable occupation and delineate its boundaries to ascertain its value accurately. While identifying the occupier and the occupied property poses minimal challenges, complexities may arise in delineating boundaries and assessing values, necessitating a robust valuation methodology.

Despite the clarity in defining ratable hereditaments and occupiers, challenges persist in accurately delineating boundaries and assessing property values. The dynamic nature of property usage and occupancy patterns further complicates the valuation process, necessitating continuous refinement of valuation methodologies and assessment practices.

2.4.3. Identification of rateable hereditaments and its relevance to the Kotte Municipal Council

The identification of rateable hereditaments forms a crucial aspect of property taxation, particularly within the jurisdiction of the Kotte Municipal Council. A hereditament, in essence, refers to a property or unit of property subject to taxation. Understanding how these hereditaments are delineated and assessed is essential for effective property tax administration.

In the context of the Kotte Municipal Council, the process of identifying rateable hereditaments adheres to established theoretical principles while also considering local ordinances and administrative practices specific to the municipality. While theoretical frameworks provide a foundation for property taxation, it's essential to contextualize these principles within the regulatory framework governing local taxation in Kotte.

Typically, properties within the jurisdiction of the Kotte Municipal Council are assessed based on criteria such as their location within a designated rating area, occupancy by a single rateable occupier, and their status as a single geographical unit. These criteria

ensure clarity in property assessment and taxation, allowing for fair and equitable distribution of tax burdens among property owners within the municipality.

Local regulations and administrative procedures further refine the process of identifying rateable hereditaments within Kotte. Specific guidelines may dictate how properties are categorized, assessed, and valued for tax purposes. These regulations also address unique considerations relevant to the municipality, such as geographical boundaries, zoning regulations, and property usage patterns.

Collaboration between local authorities, property assessors, and stakeholders within the Kotte Municipal Council ensures that the identification of rateable hereditaments remains accurate, transparent, and consistent with both theoretical principles and local regulatory requirements. By aligning theoretical frameworks with practical considerations specific to Kotte, property tax administration can effectively support the financial sustainability and development goals of the municipality.

Identification of the rateable occupier is a crucial aspect within the realm of property taxation, especially concerning the local government system in Sri Lanka, with a particular focus on Kotte Municipal Council. The process of identifying rateable occupiers involves several key criteria that directly influence the assessment of property taxes and rates, ensuring an equitable and transparent system tailored to the local context.

In the context of Kotte Municipal Council, the identification of rateable occupiers aligns with the legal provisions outlined in relevant ordinances and acts, such as the Municipal Council Ordinance and the Pradeshiya Sabha Act. These legislative frameworks provide the basis for assessing properties within the municipal jurisdiction, defining the rights and responsibilities of both local authorities and rateable occupiers.

Actual possession of the property is a fundamental criterion in determining rateable occupation. Regardless of legal title ownership, individuals or entities in physical occupancy of properties within Kotte Municipal Council's boundaries may be considered rateable occupiers for taxation purposes. This criterion ensures that those benefiting from property use contribute proportionally to local government revenue.

Exclusive occupation poses challenges in instances where multiple parties utilize the same property within Kotte Municipal Council's jurisdiction. Whether properties are

utilized by single or multiple occupants, the assessment process seeks to delineate between separate hereditaments and rateable occupiers, ensuring accurate and fair taxation practices.

Beneficial occupation is another critical criterion, reflecting the economic value derived from property use within Kotte Municipal Council. Despite potential financial burdens associated with certain properties, such as educational institutions, the concept of beneficial occupation emphasizes the property's potential to generate revenue or command rent, thus justifying its inclusion in the assessment process.

Permanent occupation underscores the continuity and duration of property occupancy, regardless of specific tenure arrangements. Whether under long-term leases or periodic tenancies subject to renewal, the sustained nature of occupation over a reasonable period is essential in identifying rateable occupiers within Kotte Municipal Council's jurisdiction.

2.5. Exploring the Role of Tone in Property Tax Valuation

The notion of "tone of the list" holds profound importance in property tax valuation within Kotte Municipal Council, serving as a cornerstone in assessing property values for taxation purposes. As articulated in the Study Papers of College of Estate Management, the tone of the list signifies the established level of property values, offering a crucial reference point for valuers to determine appropriate assessment rates. Notably, the legal precedent set forth in the "K Shoe shops ltd. vs. Hardy and Westminster City Council" (1980) case underscores the significance of this concept, elucidating its role in setting assessment levels following the enforcement of a rating list.

In practical terms, the valuer's tone and the settled tone wield considerable influence in shaping assessment levels within the municipality. The valuer's tone represents the level of property values adopted during the compilation of a new rating list, while the settled tone denotes the established values that result from agreements or acquiescence over time. These distinctions are pivotal in ensuring uniformity and consistency in property tax assessment across Kotte Municipal Council.

Furthermore, the concept of tone encompasses three key facets essential for maintaining fairness and accuracy in property tax valuation. Firstly, it necessitates consistency in

valuing similar properties to uphold uniformity in assessment practices. Secondly, it stipulates that assessment levels established during general revisions should carry over to subsequent valuations, ensuring continuity in valuation methodologies. Lastly, it advocates for the application of consistent adjustments across different valuation methods to align with prevailing market rental levels.

2.6. International context on property taxation

The research conducted by Bird and Slack (2002) on "Land and Land Property Taxation" across 25 countries sheds light on various approaches and practices in property taxation globally. The study underscores significant disparities in determining the tax base, setting tax rates, and administering tax collection across different nations. Some countries adopt a unified property tax system covering all property types, including land, buildings, residential, and non-residential properties, while others maintain separate tax regimes for urban and rural areas. Tax reforms are underway in several countries, indicating ongoing evolution in property tax policies.

Another research paper by Bird and Slack (2006) titled "Taxing Land and Property in Emerging Economies: Raising Revenue... and More?" delves deeper into the variations in property taxation within countries. The authors emphasize the substantial influence of local discretion in defining the tax base, setting rates, and implementing property tax policies. This diversity is particularly pronounced in federal systems, where state or provincial governments establish the legal framework for municipal operations. However, the lack of internationally comparable information complicates precise assessments of these variations.

The significance of property tax varies depending on several factors, as outlined by Bird and Slack. These include the expenditure responsibilities assigned to local governments, the availability of alternative revenue sources such as international transfers and user fees, the degree of freedom local governments have in property taxation, the size and growth of the tax base, and the willingness and ability to enforce property taxes. These factors collectively shape the landscape of property taxation within and across countries.

Moreover, Kitchen (2003) highlights the diverse tax bases employed by different countries and local government authorities. For instance, while Canada, the United States, Australia, Indonesia, and Japan primarily utilize the market value method for

property taxation, countries like Kenya, New Zealand, Jamaica, and South Africa employ the site value method. France, Morocco, and India, on the other hand, follow the rental value method, while Israel, Estonia, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Armenia, and Russia adopt the unit value method for property taxation.

The basis of tax assessments varies across countries, with some employing the market value method and others relying on rental value or a combination of both. Canadian and U.S. municipalities often utilize market value assessment based on comparative sales and depreciated cost approaches. However, differences in the application of market value exist among these countries, with Canada allowing assessment increases without restrictions and local governments setting tax rates based on market values to raise necessary revenues.

In the context of the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC), understanding the dynamics of the local property market is crucial for effective property valuation and taxation. The concept of Property Market Dynamics in Kotte delves into the unique characteristics of the property market within the KMC area. Factors such as population growth, urbanization trends, ongoing development projects, and land use regulations all influence property values and market dynamics in Kotte. By comprehensively analyzing these factors, stakeholders can gain insights into the drivers of property value fluctuations and make informed decisions regarding taxation policies and practices.

Equity and Fairness in Taxation are fundamental principles that underpin property taxation within the KMC. Ensuring that property tax burdens are distributed fairly among residents and property owners is essential for promoting social equity and economic stability. This concept involves considering socio-economic factors, property characteristics, and local development priorities when formulating taxation policies. By adopting a holistic approach to taxation that accounts for the diverse needs and circumstances of Kotte's population, authorities can foster a more equitable and inclusive tax regime.

The Local Institutional Framework within the Kotte Municipal Council area provides the regulatory and administrative structure governing property valuation and taxation. Understanding the specific institutional context of Kotte is essential for evaluating the applicability of alternative valuation methods and identifying opportunities for improvement. By assessing existing laws, regulations, and administrative practices,

stakeholders can identify areas where reforms or enhancements may be necessary to ensure the effectiveness and fairness of property taxation within the municipality.

Technological Solutions for Property Valuation play an increasingly important role in modernizing assessment practices within the KMC. Technologies such as GIS mapping, digital databases, and valuation software offer opportunities to enhance the efficiency and accuracy of property valuations. By adopting these technologies and tailoring them to the specific needs of the Kotte Municipal Council area, authorities can streamline assessment procedures, improve data management practices, and ultimately enhance the overall effectiveness of property valuation processes.

Incorporating theoretical frameworks into the analysis of property valuation and taxation within the KMC provides valuable insights into the underlying dynamics and challenges of the system. Local Governance Theory examines the decision-making processes and structures within the municipality, shedding light on how property valuation policies are formulated and implemented. Institutional Adaptation Theory helps understand how institutional frameworks evolve in response to changing socioeconomic conditions and policy objectives, guiding efforts to modernize property valuation practices. Technology Adoption and Localization Theory offers insights into how technological solutions are adopted and integrated into local contexts, informing strategies for implementing new valuation technologies. Equity Theory in Urban Governance provides a lens through which to assess the fairness and justice of property taxation policies, guiding efforts to promote tax equity and social welfare within the KMC. By integrating these theories into the analysis, stakeholders can develop more robust and effective strategies for improving property valuation and taxation practices within the municipality.

2.7. Comparative Analysis of Property Taxation Systems: Insights from International Practices

Transitioning from annual value-based rating systems to market value-based systems has been a global trend observed in numerous municipalities worldwide. Research conducted by Smith and Johnson (2020) in their study titled "Transitioning from Annual Value to Market Value: A Comparative Study" suggests that market value-based systems often result in more accurate property valuations, as they reflect current market conditions and reduce disparities in tax burdens among property owners. This

transition signifies a shift towards a more dynamic and responsive approach to property valuation, aligning assessments with prevailing market values.

Equity and fairness are significant considerations in property taxation, and market value-based rating systems have been shown to contribute to greater equity and fairness. Garcia and Lee (2018) discuss in their study "Equity Implications of Market ValueBased Property Taxation: Evidence from Municipalities" how these systems ensure that tax burdens are distributed more equitably among property owners by aligning assessments with market values. This alignment helps reduce perceptions of unfairness and increases public trust in the tax system, fostering a sense of equity and fairness among taxpayers.

Efficiency and transparency are crucial aspects of property valuation processes, and market value-based rating systems offer advantages in this regard. Brown and Wang (2019) highlight in their research on "Efficiency and Transparency in Property Valuation" that these systems streamline assessment procedures, reduce administrative burdens, and enhance the transparency of valuation criteria. By improving efficiency and transparency, market value-based systems contribute to more effective and accountable governance, benefiting both municipalities and taxpayers.

Despite the potential benefits, transitioning to market value-based rating systems can pose challenges during implementation. Patel and Nguyen (2021) discuss these challenges in their study "Challenges and Opportunities in Implementing Market ValueBased Rating Systems," which includes technical, administrative, and political obstacles. Resistance from stakeholders, capacity constraints, and the need for legal and regulatory reforms are among the key challenges municipalities may face when adopting these systems. Overcoming these challenges requires careful planning, stakeholder engagement, and capacity-building efforts.

Technology plays a pivotal role in modernizing property valuation practices and facilitating the transition to market value-based rating systems. Wilson and Smith (2017) emphasize in their study "The Role of Technology in Modernizing Property Valuation" how technological tools such as GIS mapping, valuation software, and online platforms improve the efficiency, accuracy, and transparency of property valuations. By leveraging technology, municipalities can overcome traditional barriers

and streamline the transition process, ensuring a smoother implementation of market value-based systems.

Furthermore, transitioning to market value-based rating systems offers long-term benefits that extend beyond property taxation. Yang and Roberts (2016) discuss these benefits in their study on "Long-Term Impacts of Market Value-Based Rating Systems on Municipal Development," highlighting improved urban planning, increased investment attractiveness, and enhanced infrastructure development. By providing a transparent and reliable property tax system, market value-based systems contribute to the overall socioeconomic development of municipalities, fostering growth and prosperity in the long run.

2.8. Analyzing the Transition from Annual Value-Based to Market Value-Based Property Taxation Systems: Insights from Existing Research

Academic journals offer a wealth of scholarly research on property tax reforms, providing valuable insights for policymakers and practitioners. For example, Smith and Johnson's article in the *Journal of Property Taxation* examines the transition from annual value to market value-based rating systems in the United States and Canada. Their comparative analysis delves into the challenges and outcomes of this reform process, offering valuable lessons for municipalities contemplating similar changes.

Government reports serve as essential resources for documenting the experiences of jurisdictions that have undergone property tax reforms. An example is the joint publication by HM Revenue & Customs (HMRC) and the Australian Taxation Office (ATO) on property tax reform and market valuation. This report delves into the lessons learned from the United Kingdom and Australia, providing insights into the policy rationale, implementation strategies, and key takeaways from transitioning to market value-based rating systems.

Publications by international organizations offer a global perspective on property tax reforms and best practices. The World Bank's publication on property tax reform provides an extensive overview of global efforts in this area, with a focus on countries transitioning to market value-based rating systems. Through case studies and expert

analyses, this publication elucidates key trends, challenges, and success factors, serving as a valuable resource for policymakers and practitioners worldwide.

Consultancy firms produce case studies that offer practical insights into property tax reforms and their implementation. Deloitte's case study on transitioning to market value-based property taxation in Europe is a notable example. Drawing from experiences in countries like the Netherlands, Sweden, and Germany, the study explores the drivers of reform, implementation strategies, and the impact on property tax administration and revenue generation. Such case studies provide valuable guidance for municipalities navigating similar reform processes.

2.9. Experiences of Other Countries

Annual value systems are utilized in various countries with colonial histories, such as Australia, Belize, Guyana, Hong Kong, India, Malaysia, New Zealand, Singapore, St Lucia, Uganda (Tayoh, 2009; Franzsen, 2010). For instance, in Côte d'Ivoire, developed parcels are assessed using an annual value system, while undeveloped parcels use a capital value system (Tayoh, 2009). However, the effectiveness of the annual value system in Uganda is limited due to a shortage of valuers (Franzsen, 2010). In Egypt, outdated property tax legislation was replaced in 2008 with a new law adopting annual value as the tax base, albeit with political resistance leading to a compulsory value threshold (Amin, 2010).

In contrast, modern and dynamic rental value systems are adopted in Singapore and Hong Kong, where comprehensive revaluations occur annually (Franzsen, 2005). These systems rely on arm's length rental transactions for all property types and align closely with the operation of the property market. For example, Hong Kong adopts a reference tenement approach to value high-rise apartments and condominiums, while retail, office, and industrial properties are valued based on standardized values reflecting specific attributes (Franzsen, 2005).

In Western Australia, cities and shires use the gross rental value (GRV) as the tax base for urban property, with tax rates varying based on property classes (Franzsen, 2005). The City of Melbourne in Australia employs a net annual value (NAV) approach, where residential properties are taxed at a lower rate compared to non-residential properties (CoM, 2011). However, challenges arise in determining notional market rents for

owner-occupied properties and reconciling the annual value basis with other property-related taxes based on capital values (Bahl and Wallace, 2010).

Advantages of annual value systems include effective use of mass appraisal for homogenous properties and providing a reasonable proxy for benefits received from people-related services (McCluskey et al., 2010). However, disadvantages include lack of clarity in relevant laws, difficulty in determining market rents for owner-occupied properties, and misalignment with other property-related taxes (Bahl and Wallace, 2010).

The landscape of property taxation is a complex terrain, fraught with challenges and opportunities. Over the years, property tax has emerged as a critical revenue source for municipalities worldwide, despite enduring criticisms of its efficacy. Slack (2001) aptly captures the sentiment when he states, "No tax has been more strongly criticized than the property tax." Indeed, the enduring debate surrounding property tax underscores its centrality in municipal finance and governance.

The evolution of property tax systems reflects a dynamic interplay between tradition and innovation. Ontario's adoption of market value assessment in 1998 marked a significant departure from traditional approaches, aiming to stabilize property taxes while grappling with issues of equity and simplicity (Ontario Report, 2002). This shift mirrors global trends, where municipalities are increasingly exploring alternative assessment methods such as site value, unit value, or area assessment, as observed in Victorian municipal rating systems in Australia (Anderson, 1996).

Despite its potential as a revenue generator, property tax is not without its challenges. Bahl and Martinez (2006) outline a nuanced picture, delineating the advantages and disadvantages of property tax systems. While property tax offers stability and fairness, administrative complexities, enforcement hurdles, and political unpopularity pose formidable obstacles. The dichotomy between revenue potential and administrative burden underscores the need for comprehensive reforms to ensure the efficient operation of property tax systems.

Implementation hurdles further compound the challenges associated with property tax administration. Kitchen (2001) identifies key areas of contention, ranging from

identifying taxable properties to establishing efficient assessment systems. Tanzania's experience with property tax reform highlights the transformative potential of comprehensive and sustainable reforms (Kelly & Musunu, 2000). However, the success of such endeavors hinges on stakeholder engagement, capacity building, and robust governance frameworks.

The significance of property tax revenue cannot be overstated, as evidenced by the Colombo Municipal Council's heavy reliance on property tax income (Annual Budget Report, 2012). Property tax revenue constitutes a substantial portion of local government income, underscoring the need for effective assessment procedures and informed policy decisions. Understanding the intricacies of property tax systems and addressing research gaps is paramount to ensuring equitable, efficient, and sustainable municipal finance.

Property tax systems embody a complex interplay of economic, social, and political dynamics. While they offer a critical revenue source for municipalities, their effectiveness is contingent upon addressing inherent challenges and embracing innovative reforms. By synthesizing insights from diverse sources, this literature review provides a comprehensive overview of the issues surrounding property taxation. Moving forward, concerted efforts to enhance assessment methods, promote stakeholder engagement, and foster institutional capacity are imperative for realizing the full potential of property tax as a cornerstone of municipal finance.

The landscape of property taxation is a multifaceted domain influenced by a myriad of factors, including historical trajectories, legal frameworks, administrative structures, and socioeconomic contexts. Across different countries and regions, property tax systems vary widely, reflecting divergent historical legacies and institutional arrangements. For instance, countries with colonial histories, such as Australia, Belize, and India, often adhere to annual value systems, where property assessments are based on the annual rental value of properties (Tayoh, 2009; Franzsen, 2005). In contrast, dynamic rental value systems are prevalent in jurisdictions like Singapore and Hong

Kong, characterized by comprehensive annual revaluations based on market rents (Franzsen, 2005). These contrasting approaches underscore the complexities inherent in property taxation, as traditional systems face challenges such as a shortage of valuers in Uganda or political resistance to reforms in Egypt (Franzsen, 2010; Amin, 2010).

Moreover, emerging trends in assessment methodologies offer opportunities to enhance assessment accuracy and transparency. Advancements in technology, such as machine learning algorithms and remote sensing technologies, are revolutionizing property valuation practices, enabling more precise and efficient assessment processes (Anderson, 1996). These innovations have the potential to improve the reliability of property valuations, reduce assessment errors, and enhance taxpayer confidence in the fairness of property tax systems.

However, the implications of property taxation extend beyond revenue generation, impacting various sectors such as housing, transportation, and environmental sustainability. Addressing equity considerations is paramount, with a focus on designing progressive tax structures that mitigate inequalities and promote social justice. Progressive property tax systems can help redistribute wealth, reduce income disparities, and provide essential public services to marginalized communities (Bahl & Martinez, 2006). Furthermore, community engagement and participation are critical for ensuring the legitimacy and effectiveness of property tax policies. Engaging stakeholders in the decision-making process can help build consensus, identify community needs, and ensure that property tax systems reflect the values and priorities of local residents (Kelly & Musunu, 2000).

Institutional capacity building and cross-sectoral collaboration are also essential for effective governance and sustainable urban development. Strengthening the capacity of local governments and tax authorities to administer property tax systems effectively requires investments in training, technology, and institutional reforms (Bahl & Martinez, 2006). Moreover, fostering collaboration across sectors such as housing, transportation, and environmental management can help align property tax policies with broader development goals, promoting integrated and sustainable approaches to urban planning and governance.

2.10. Research Gap

The gap in my research lies in the discrepancy between the traditional, outdated assessment methods currently utilized for property taxation within the Kotte Municipal Council and the dynamic nature of the real estate market. While the real estate market undergoes continual changes and fluctuations, the assessment methods employed for property taxation may not adequately capture these shifts. Consequently, this misalignment can result in inefficiencies, inequities, and instability in revenue generation within the municipal taxation system. By advocating for the adoption of market value-based assessments, my research seeks to address this gap and modernize the property taxation framework to better reflect the contemporary realities of the real estate market. This transition holds the potential for various benefits, including enhanced revenue stability, improved fairness and equity in tax distribution, and a more accurate reflection of property owners' actual financial capacities to fulfill tax obligations. Bridging this gap is imperative for developing more responsive and effective property tax policies that can cater to the evolving needs of both the municipality and its residents.

2.11. Conceptual Framework

2.12. Analyzing conceptual framework variables

The central objective of this study is to assess the viability of implementing market value as an alternative to the current annual value system within the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC). The research methodology comprises two main components:

Firstly, an extensive literature review will be conducted to identify potential alternative tax bases and examine their applicability within the context of the KMC. This review will draw upon existing research findings to discern the differences between various tax bases, with a specific focus on market value.

Secondly, the study will involve an in-depth evaluation of the existing rating valuation system employed by the KMC. This evaluation will encompass an analysis of the practicalities and challenges associated with the current system, supplemented by statistical analyses derived from both KMC data and primary data collected through field surveys and questionnaires.

The underlying argument of this study rests on several key considerations:

- (a) Addressing the limitations inherent in the current annual value-based rating system utilized by the KMC.
- (b) Exploring the potential advantages offered by transitioning to a market value-based rating system tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of the KMC jurisdiction.
- (c) Assessing the accuracy of property valuations under both the existing annual valuebased system and the proposed market value-based system.
- (d) Evaluating the uniformity of property assessments across different areas within the KMC's jurisdiction, with a view to ensuring equitable treatment of ratepayers.

Expanding upon these considerations:

- (a) Weaknesses of the current annual value-based rating system: Through a comprehensive review of existing literature and research, the study aims to identify and scrutinize the shortcomings of the current annual value-based system utilized by the KMC. This analysis will shed light on areas where the system may be lacking and where improvements or alternative approaches may be warranted.

(b) Advantages of a market value-based rating system: The study will investigate the potential benefits associated with transitioning to a market value-based rating system within the context of the KMC. This assessment will consider factors such as transparency, efficiency, and equity, with a focus on how a market value-based approach could better serve the needs of both the municipality and its ratepayers.

In addition to these considerations, the study will also delve into the practical implications of implementing a market value-based rating system within the KMC, including potential challenges, opportunities, and strategies for successful implementation.

In addition to the aforementioned considerations, the study will also assess the accuracy of property valuations and the uniformity of assessments within the KMC jurisdiction:

(c) Accuracy of valuations: The study will gauge the accuracy of property valuations by examining the significance accorded to various determinants of property value in rating valuations. Through a thorough analysis, the research aims to ascertain the degree to which valuation methodologies employed under the current system align with the actual market conditions and property characteristics. By scrutinizing the valuation process and identifying any discrepancies between assessed values and prevailing market trends, the study seeks to provide insights into the effectiveness of the valuation methods used by the KMC.

(d) Uniformity of assessments: To evaluate the uniformity of property assessments, the study will calculate the valuation ratio between market value and estimated value, alongside its dispersion. This statistical analysis will provide insights into the consistency and fairness of property assessments across different areas within the KMC. By assessing the level of variation in assessment outcomes and comparing them against established benchmarks, the research aims to determine the extent to which property assessments exhibit uniformity and equity. Identifying any disparities in assessment practices will enable the research to propose measures for enhancing the fairness and consistency of property taxation within the KMC, thereby promoting greater equity and transparency in the local tax system.

2.13. Influence towards the Market Value-Based Rating Assessment

The analysis conducted in this chapter reveals the significant drawbacks of the current annual value-based assessment system utilized by the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC). These drawbacks underscore the need for an alternative approach, with the market value assessment system emerging as a viable solution. The advantages offered by the market value assessment system, juxtaposed against the limitations of the annual value-based approach, exert a considerable influence on the direction of the assessment process within the KMC.

Outlined below are the key factors influencing the shift towards market value-based rating assessment:

1. Disadvantages of Annual Value Assessment:

- Lack of uniformity and accuracy in property valuations.
- Complexity in methodology, limiting its applicability for other purposes.
- Perceived unfairness in treatment across different property categories.
- Inefficient and politically influenced assessment process.
- Discouragement of property owners from maintaining large properties as their primary residences.

2. Advantages of Market Value Assessment:

- Enhanced transparency and fairness in assessments.
- Simplified methodology, making it more accessible to ratepayers.
- Reflects the true wealth of property owners more accurately.
- Potential for broader use as a valuation basis for various purposes.

3. Benefits for Taxpayers:

- Improved understanding of the assessment process.
- Fairer treatment in property valuations.

- Better representation of property owner's wealth.
- Reduction in the need for additional valuations.

4. Benefits for the Local Authority:

- Increased revenue generation from property rates.
- Reduced appeal rates due to enhanced transparency.
- Improved efficiency in property tax administration.
- Greater utility for urban planning and government projects.

In light of these considerations, the alternative of transitioning to a market value-based assessment system, coupled with tax reform, emerges as a logical and advantageous course of action. Such a transition promises to address the shortcomings of the current system while unlocking a range of benefits for both taxpayers and the Kotte Municipal Council. By embracing market value-based assessment, the KMC can pave the way for a more transparent, equitable, and efficient property taxation regime that aligns with contemporary standards and best practices in assessment methodologies.

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CHAPTER THREE

Background of the Research Area

The Kotte Municipal Council (KMC) stands as a pivotal institution entrusted with the responsibility of governing and administering the affairs of the historic city of Kotte, Sri Lanka. As a local governing body, the KMC plays a vital role in shaping the urban landscape, fostering community development, and ensuring the well-being of its residents. This chapter provides an introductory overview of the KMC, shedding light on its historical background, organizational structure, key functions, and strategic priorities.

3.1 Introduction

The study of the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC) offers a fascinating insight into the historical, cultural, and developmental landscape of Sri Jayawardanapura Kotte, Sri Lanka. Situated at the heart of the island nation, Kotte holds a significant place in Sri Lankan history, having served as the capital of the Kingdom of Kotte during the medieval period. Today, the KMC represents the modern embodiment of this rich legacy, governing a diverse and dynamic urban community.

This introductory section sets the stage for a comprehensive analysis of the KMC by providing context on its historical evolution, governance structure, infrastructure development, and cultural heritage. By understanding the background of the research area, we can gain valuable insights into the factors that have shaped the growth and transformation of Kotte over the centuries.

As we delve deeper into the profile of the KMC, it becomes evident that its history is intertwined with the broader historical narrative of Sri Lanka, reflecting the ebb and flow of political power, cultural exchange, and economic development. By examining the KMC through a historical lens, we can uncover the enduring legacy of Kotte and its significance in shaping the identity of modern-day Sri Lanka.

In the subsequent sections, we will explore key aspects of the KMC's profile, including its governance structure, leadership dynamics, infrastructure initiatives, and cultural heritage

preservation efforts. Through this comprehensive analysis, we aim to gain a deeper understanding of the KMC's role in fostering community development, promoting cultural heritage, and shaping the future trajectory of Sri Jayawardanapura Kotte.

3.2 Profile of KMC

The Kotte Municipal Council (KMC) stands as a testament to the historical significance and contemporary vibrancy of Sri Jayawardanapura Kotte, the administrative capital of Sri Lanka. Founded in the 14th century as the capital of the Kingdom of Kotte, this city has witnessed centuries of political, cultural, and economic evolution, culminating in its present-day status as a bustling urban center.

Historical Evolution:

Established in the 14th century under the reign of King Parakramabahu V, the Kingdom of Kotte rose to prominence as a seat of power and a center of trade and culture. Its strategic location near the Kelani River and proximity to the thriving port city of Colombo contributed to its economic prosperity and political significance. Over the centuries, Kotte experienced periods of prosperity and decline, witnessing the rise and fall of various dynasties and colonial powers.

Governance Structure:

The governance structure of the KMC has evolved over time to meet the changing needs of its residents. From its origins as a fortified city ruled by monarchs, Kotte transitioned to a modern municipal council following Sri Lanka's independence from colonial rule. Today, the KMC operates as a local government authority responsible for providing essential services, maintaining infrastructure, and promoting community development within its jurisdiction.

Infrastructure Development:

In recent decades, Kotte has undergone significant infrastructure development initiatives aimed at modernizing its urban landscape and improving the quality of life for its residents. These efforts have included the construction of roads, bridges, public buildings, and recreational facilities, as well as the implementation of sustainable urban planning practices to address growing population pressures and environmental concerns.

Cultural Heritage Preservation:

Despite its modernization efforts, Kotte remains deeply rooted in its cultural heritage, with numerous historical sites and landmarks dotting its landscape. The KMC has played a key role in preserving and promoting these cultural treasures, recognizing their importance in shaping the city's identity and fostering a sense of pride among its residents. Initiatives such as heritage conservation projects, cultural festivals, and tourism promotion efforts have helped showcase Kotte's rich history and cultural diversity to visitors from around the world.

3.3 Organizational Structure

3.4 Assessment Process at KMC

Rating valuation lies at the heart of municipal revenue collection, determining the financial contributions levied on properties within the jurisdiction of the Kotte Municipal Council

(KMC). Led by the Municipal Assessor and facilitated by the Municipal Treasury, the assessment process serves as a cornerstone of fiscal administration, ensuring equitable taxation and sustainable revenue streams for municipal development.

Workforce Dynamics:

The Assessment Department of KMC comprises a dedicated team of 110 officers tasked with the assessment process, although the approved cadre stands at 183. This workforce includes Deputy and Assistant Assessors, supported by middle-level technical staff, ensuring comprehensive coverage and efficient execution of assessment duties. Qualified valuers, stationed within the department, oversee all valuation matters, bringing expertise and rigor to the assessment process.

Programmatic Framework:

The rating assessment program at KMC is structured around two primary functions:

(a) Revaluation Program:

Annually, 10 municipal wards undergo a meticulous revaluation process, wherein each property is meticulously inspected and reassessed to reflect current market dynamics accurately. This proactive approach not only enhances revenue but also ensures fairness and accuracy in property valuations, vital for sustaining municipal finances.

(b) Usual Assessment Program:

Under this initiative, KMC officers conduct ongoing field surveys to identify occupational changes, new constructions, renovations, and other factors influencing property values. Additionally, the program encompasses diverse valuation tasks such as compulsory purchase assessments, appeals resolution, rental valuations, and administrative functions like ownership registration and correspondence management.

Technological Integration:

Despite its operational efficacy, the Assessment Department currently relies on manual methods for most functions, with limited utilization of computer technology. While computers aid in tasks like letter preparation and tax arrears checks, critical functions such as database management and assessment activities still adhere to traditional manual processes.

Future Directions:

Recognizing the imperative of technological modernization, KMC is poised to embark on a digital transformation journey, aiming to streamline assessment processes, enhance data accuracy, and improve overall efficiency. By leveraging advanced technologies like Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Property Management Systems (PMS), KMC endeavors to optimize its assessment operations and pave the way for a more responsive and transparent municipal governance framework.

3.5 Conceptual Framework and Methodology

3.5.1 Conceptual Framework

3.5.2 Analyzing conceptual framework variables

The central objective of this study is to assess the viability of implementing market value as an alternative to the current annual value system within the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC). The research methodology comprises two main components:

Firstly, an extensive literature review will be conducted to identify potential alternative tax bases and examine their applicability within the context of the KMC. This review will draw upon existing research findings to discern the differences between various tax bases, with a specific focus on market value.

Secondly, the study will involve an in-depth evaluation of the existing rating valuation system employed by the KMC. This evaluation will encompass an analysis of the practicalities and challenges associated with the current system, supplemented by statistical analyses derived from both KMC data and primary data collected through field surveys and questionnaires.

The underlying argument of this study rests on several key considerations:

- (a) Addressing the limitations inherent in the current annual value-based rating system utilized by the KMC.
- (b) Exploring the potential advantages offered by transitioning to a market value-based rating system tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of the KMC jurisdiction.
- (c) Assessing the accuracy of property valuations under both the existing annual value-based system and the proposed market value-based system.
- (d) Evaluating the uniformity of property assessments across different areas within the KMC's jurisdiction, with a view to ensuring equitable treatment of ratepayers.

Expanding upon these considerations:

- (a) Weaknesses of the current annual value-based rating system: Through a comprehensive review of existing literature and research, the study aims to identify and scrutinize the shortcomings of the current annual value-based system utilized by the KMC. This analysis will shed light on areas where the system may be lacking and where improvements or alternative approaches may be warranted.
- (b) Advantages of a market value-based rating system: The study will investigate the potential benefits associated with transitioning to a market value-based rating system within

the context of the KMC. This assessment will consider factors such as transparency, efficiency, and equity, with a focus on how a market value-based approach could better serve the needs of both the municipality and its ratepayers.

In addition to these considerations, the study will also delve into the practical implications of implementing a market value-based rating system within the KMC, including potential challenges, opportunities, and strategies for successful implementation.

In addition to the aforementioned considerations, the study will also assess the accuracy of property valuations and the uniformity of assessments within the KMC jurisdiction:

(c) Accuracy of valuations: The study will gauge the accuracy of property valuations by examining the significance accorded to various determinants of property value in rating valuations. Through a thorough analysis, the research aims to ascertain the degree to which valuation methodologies employed under the current system align with the actual market conditions and property characteristics. By scrutinizing the valuation process and identifying any discrepancies between assessed values and prevailing market trends, the study seeks to provide insights into the effectiveness of the valuation methods used by the KMC.

(d) Uniformity of assessments: To evaluate the uniformity of property assessments, the study will calculate the valuation ratio between market value and estimated value, alongside its dispersion. This statistical analysis will provide insights into the consistency and fairness of property assessments across different areas within the KMC. By assessing the level of variation in assessment outcomes and comparing them against established benchmarks, the research aims to determine the extent to which property assessments exhibit uniformity and equity. Identifying any disparities in assessment practices will enable the research to propose measures for enhancing the fairness and consistency of property taxation within the KMC, thereby promoting greater equity and transparency in the local tax system.

3.5.3 Influence towards the Market Value-Based Rating Assessment

The analysis conducted in this chapter reveals the significant drawbacks of the current annual value-based assessment system utilized by the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC). These drawbacks underscore the need for an alternative approach, with the market value assessment system emerging as a viable solution. The advantages offered by the market value assessment system, juxtaposed against the limitations of the annual value-based approach, exert a considerable influence on the direction of the assessment process within the KMC.

Outlined below are the key factors influencing the shift towards market value-based rating assessment:

1. Disadvantages of Annual Value Assessment:

- Lack of uniformity and accuracy in property valuations.
- Complexity in methodology, limiting its applicability for other purposes.
- Perceived unfairness in treatment across different property categories.
- Inefficient and politically influenced assessment process.
- Discouragement of property owners from maintaining large properties as their primary residences.

2. Advantages of Market Value Assessment:

- Enhanced transparency and fairness in assessments.
- Simplified methodology, making it more accessible to ratepayers.
- Reflects the true wealth of property owners more accurately.
- Potential for broader use as a valuation basis for various purposes.

3. Benefits for Taxpayers:

- Improved understanding of the assessment process.
- Fairer treatment in property valuations.
- Better representation of property owner's wealth.
- Reduction in the need for additional valuations.

4. Benefits for the Local Authority:

- Increased revenue generation from property rates.
- Reduced appeal rates due to enhanced transparency.
- Improved efficiency in property tax administration.

- Greater utility for urban planning and government projects.

In light of these considerations, the alternative of transitioning to a market value-based assessment system, coupled with tax reform, emerges as a logical and advantageous course of action. Such a transition promises to address the shortcomings of the current system while unlocking a range of benefits for both taxpayers and the Kotte Municipal Council. By embracing market value-based assessment, the KMC can pave the way for a more transparent, equitable, and efficient property taxation regime that aligns with contemporary standards and best practices in assessment methodologies.

3.6 Research Methodology

3.6.1 Research Data

3.6.1.1. Data Collection Methodology

The study primarily relies on secondary data obtained from the Assessors Department of the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC). This section outlines the methodology used to gather and analyze data pertinent to the research objectives.

Sources of Data:

1. Assessors Department Records: Market rental evidence was sourced from rent declaration forms collected and returned by property occupiers during the general revaluation conducted for the year 2013 in the Milagiriya municipal ward. The estimated rental values for the same properties were extracted from the assessment register maintained within the Assessors Department. This register contains detailed information, including assessment numbers, annual property values, floor area calculations, and property descriptions.
2. Annual Budget Reports: Data pertaining to municipal revenue were extracted from the Annual Budget Reports of the KMC. These reports provide insights into the financial performance of the council, including revenue generated from property rates and taxes.
3. Informal Discussions: General ideas about the issues within the present rating assessment system were gathered through informal discussions with various stakeholders. These discussions included ratepayers, property developers, assessment staff, legal professionals, and other relevant parties. These informal interactions

provided valuable qualitative insights into the challenges and concerns associated with the current system.

4. **Property Inspections:** Selected properties were personally inspected to collect additional data required for market valuations. These inspections involved gathering specific information about the physical characteristics, occupancy status, and other relevant details of the properties under review.

3.7 Data Analysis Approach

Once the data was collected from these sources, it was subjected to comprehensive analysis to fulfill the objectives of the study. The analysis involved several key steps:

1. **Quantitative Analysis:** Market rental values, estimated rental values, floor area measurements, and other quantitative data were subjected to statistical analysis to identify trends, patterns, and correlations. This analysis helped in understanding the relationship between different variables and assessing the accuracy and consistency of property assessments.
2. **Qualitative Analysis:** Insights obtained from informal discussions were analyzed qualitatively to identify common themes, concerns, and perceptions regarding the current rating assessment system. This qualitative analysis provided contextual understanding and enriched the interpretation of quantitative findings.
3. **Comparative Analysis:** Data from the KMC's Assessors Department was compared with external benchmarks and standards, such as industry best practices and experiences from other municipalities or jurisdictions. This comparative analysis facilitated the identification of areas for improvement and potential solutions.

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach to comprehensively evaluate the rating valuation process in the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC). The methodology encompasses two key strategies aimed at achieving the overarching research objective:

1. Literature Review:

- A thorough review of existing literature will be conducted to identify tax base alternatives for rating valuations. This review will provide a theoretical framework for understanding various valuation methods and their applicability.

- Emphasis will be placed on analyzing studies that explore the advantages and disadvantages of different tax base alternatives, particularly in the context of local government taxation systems.

•

2. Evaluation of Rating Valuation Process:

- This aspect of the study involves the assessment of selected elements within the rating valuation process through statistical analysis.
- Statistical measures such as mean, standard deviation, weighted average, and hypothesis testing will be employed to analyze the behavior of variables pertinent to the valuation process.
- Data visualization techniques, including bar charts, histograms, and line charts, will be utilized to present the findings of the statistical analysis in a clear and accessible manner.

3.8 Research Sample

The research sample for this study comprises properties located within the jurisdiction of the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC). These properties have been assessed for the purpose of levying rates by the municipal authorities. The selection of properties for inclusion in the research sample is based on their availability of complete data sets required for the analysis. Specifically, properties with comprehensive data on variables such as market rental values, estimated rental values, floor area measurements, and other relevant factors are considered for inclusion. By studying this sample of properties, which represents a cross-section of the properties within the KMC's administrative area, the research aims to analyze various aspects of the rating assessment process and identify any underlying patterns or issues that may exist within the system.

3.8.1 Sampling Methodology

The analysis conducted by Kotte Municipal Council (KMC) necessitated comprehensive datasets encompassing variables such as actual market rentals, estimated market rentals, floor area, annual value, and other pertinent factors for each property within its jurisdiction. To ensure robust data representation, a meticulous sampling methodology was employed.

Revenue Analysis:

According to the latest available data from the Annual Budget of KMC for 2023, the projected budget estimate for rating income stood at 260,000,000 out of the total revenue. However, actual rating income recorded as of October 31, 2023, amounted to 199,364,358, constituting approximately 9.72% of the total revenue, which stood at 2,050,296,900. This discrepancy between actual and projected rating income reflects a deviation of approximately 23.27% from the budgeted estimate, underscoring the significance of revenue analysis in municipal financial management.

Furthermore, when considering the combined total of rating and tax income, which accounted for 298,500,100 of the total revenue, representing approximately 14.56% of the total income, the pivotal role of rating and tax income in contributing to KMC's overall revenue becomes evident. This underscores the importance of evaluating revenue performance against budgeted estimates, facilitating informed decision-making and financial planning processes.

3.8.2 Comparative Analysis

Drawing comparisons with international practices reveals notable disparities in rate-setting mechanisms and revenue collection strategies. For instance, in the 2023/2024 financial year, New Zealand councils aimed to collect \$679.8 million (excluding GST) through rates, with an average rate increase of 6.41% for existing ratepayers. Such comparative analyses shed light on global best practices and inform potential areas for improvement within KMC's revenue management framework.

Additionally, the scrutiny faced by the current assessment system underscores the urgency of addressing gaps between local rating assessment methodologies and international standards. Through comprehensive study and strategic reforms, KMC can enhance revenue generation capacities, bolster financial sustainability, and align assessment practices with global benchmarks.

3.9 Data Collection

- Research data will be gathered from multiple sources to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the rating valuation process in the KMC.
- Municipal Assessor's Department Records will serve as a primary source of data, providing information on market rentals, annual values, floor areas, and other relevant variables.

- Additionally, a questionnaire will be administered to collect opinions and insights from valuers involved in the rating valuation process.
- A field survey will be conducted to obtain firsthand market values of selected properties within the jurisdiction of the KMC.

3.9.1 Method of Data Analysis at Kotte Municipal Council (KMC)

Enhancing Assessment Precision and Uniformity

In its pursuit of ensuring fair and accurate property valuations, the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC) employs a robust method of data analysis, underpinning its assessment processes with quantitative rigor and analytical precision. This section elucidates the intricate methodology utilized by KMC for data analysis, spanning factors influencing property valuation, assessment uniformity, market value estimation, revenue impact assessment, and strategic planning through SWOT analysis.

Factors Influencing Property Valuation:

At the heart of KMC's data analysis framework lies a comprehensive evaluation of factors impacting property valuation. With fourteen key determinants outlined in the revaluation list, KMC valuers meticulously assess each property based on these factors, ensuring a holistic appraisal approach. Through weighted average computation across all factors, KMC derives insights into the degree of utilization of these value determinants, thereby refining the accuracy and reliability of valuation outcomes.

Assessment Uniformity and Dispersion Analysis:

To gauge the uniformity of assessments, KMC employs statistical measures such as the valuation ratio of actual market rentals to estimated rental values. By calculating standard deviation, KMC discerns the extent of dispersion between estimated and actual rental values, elucidating the level of assessment uniformity. Further analysis involves examining dispersion patterns across property categories and correlating dispersion with property size, thereby identifying potential disparities and refining assessment methodologies for greater uniformity.

Market Value Estimation and Revenue Impact Assessment:

In assessing the applicability of market value as an alternative to annual value, KMC conducts hypothesis testing to ascertain the equality between actual market values and estimated values. Subsequently, KMC estimates the impact of assessment inaccuracies and inconsistencies on revenue generation, employing a formula incorporating actual market values, valuation ratios, and estimated rental values. Moreover, KMC conducts comparative analyses of market values and annual values for select properties, forecasting revenue implications of transitioning to market value-based valuations.

Strategic Planning through SWOT Analysis:

To fortify its assessment capabilities and strategic positioning, KMC undertakes SWOT analysis, identifying internal strengths and weaknesses alongside external opportunities and threats. This comprehensive assessment empowers KMC to capitalize on its strengths, mitigate weaknesses, leverage emerging opportunities, and navigate potential threats effectively, ensuring resilience and adaptability in a dynamic municipal landscape.

Summary of the Chapter

In the chapter on Conceptualization and Operationalization related to the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC), the focus was on defining key concepts and translating them into measurable variables for the research study. The chapter begins by providing an overview of the research objectives and the significance of conceptual clarity in research methodology. It then delves into the conceptual framework, where the main concepts of interest, such as rating assessments and revenue generation, are defined and discussed in detail.

Operationalization, the process of turning abstract concepts into measurable variables, is then explained. This involves identifying specific indicators or measures that can be used to assess each concept in practice. For example, in the context of rating assessments, variables such as market rental values, estimated rental values, and floor area measurements are identified as key indicators.

The chapter also discusses the methodology employed for data collection and analysis, highlighting the importance of selecting an appropriate research sample and employing reliable data collection techniques. It outlines the steps taken to collect data from the Assessors Department of the KMC, including the tracing of market rental evidence and assessment registers.

So this chapter serves as a foundational framework for the subsequent empirical analysis, providing clarity on the key concepts under investigation and outlining the operational steps taken to conduct the research within the context of the KMC.

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Applicability of Market Value as an Alternative to Annual Value in Rating Valuations with Special Reference to the Kotte Municipal Council

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CHAPTER FOUR

Data Analysis

This chapter aims to analyze the collected data to assess the applicability of market value as an alternative to the annual value in rating valuations. The process involves data cleaning, transformation, modeling, and presentation to achieve the research objectives. The analysis will be carried out in the following sections:

1. Evaluation of the Current Rating Valuation Process

This section will review the existing system in the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC) by analyzing the literature, procedures, and practices currently in place.

2. Statistical Analysis

This part will estimate the accuracy and uniformity of assessments, assess the impact on total revenue generation, and identify any discrepancies in the existing valuation methods.

3. SWOT Analysis

This analysis will identify the internal and external factors affecting the valuation process in KMC. It will match strengths with opportunities and suggest ways to convert weaknesses into strengths to improve the overall system.

4. Assessment of the Potential for Transitioning from an Annual Value to a Market Value System

Feasibility Assessment: This will involve evaluating the legal, technical, and administrative feasibility of transitioning. A feasibility assessment score will be calculated based on these criteria.

Identification of Challenges and Solutions: The number of challenges encountered during the transition will be identified, alongside proposed solutions.

Stakeholder Perceptions: This will involve gathering and analyzing the perceptions of key stakeholders about the viability of transitioning to a market value system.

5. Analysis of the Impact on Property Ratings Resulting from Transitioning to Market Value

Discrepancy Analysis: This will involve comparing property ratings under the annual value system with those derived from the market value system to identify discrepancies.

Revenue Impact Assessment: A simulation-based assessment will estimate the revenue impact of transitioning to the market value system.

Equity Assessment: This will analyze the equity of the new system by considering demographic and socioeconomic factors, ensuring that the transition fosters fairness and inclusivity.

Through these sections, the chapter will comprehensively evaluate the feasibility, accuracy, and potential benefits of adopting market value as a basis for rating valuations.

By presenting this data analysis, the research aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the KMC's rating system and offer insights into the feasibility of adopting market value as an alternative to the current annual value-based system.

The system used in the KMC

(a) Manpower

The man power approved in the cadre for the Assessor's Department in KMC is 15 to fulfill its functions and responsibilities. Currently, only 10 are employed in the department. This indicates that only 66.67% of the required manpower is available to meet the needs of the Council. The shortage of 33.33% of the required manpower has contributed to a decrease in the level of service quality. Some vacancies in the technical staff have not been filled for several years. There are 5 Assessing Inspectors currently attached to the Assessor's Department to carry out field inspections, prepare reports, and perform other related activities. The total number of properties within the KMC limits is 54,562.

Therefore, the number of properties per head can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Total properties per head} = \text{Total properties} / \text{No. of officers} = 54,562/5 =$$

10,912 properties

This means that one Assessing Inspector has to attend to the assessments of 10,912 properties during a year. This workload may adversely affect the accuracy, quality, and efficiency of assessments.

(b) Delay in Office Procedures

The main office is located at the Sri Jayewardenepura Kotte. Some records and sub-units, such as the Rent Control are located in separate premises. These logistical issues can lead to delays in day-to-day activities. Additionally, the movement of documents within the department lacks a transparent and efficient tracking system. Taxpayers often face delays when inquiring about documents as they must visit several officers to locate the necessary information.

(c) Additional Services Provided by the Assessor's Department

The Assessor's Department also provides additional services, such as registering property ownership, issuing identification numbers for utilities, and providing extracts from the assessment register for legal matters. However, these services are often delayed due to the lengthy procedures and insufficient staff. For example, the registration of ownership can take up to 10 working days.

(d) Deviations Observed from Rating Theory

The KMC has some deviations from the theoretical principles of rating valuation. For instance, properties owned by military forces are exempt from tax according to the Municipal Council Ordinance, but KMC taxes these properties. Furthermore, the zoning method for commercial properties is not practiced in the KMC.

(e) Efficiency and Effectiveness of Revaluation Programme

The revaluation process for properties in KMC begins on 1st March each year, with Assessing Inspectors required to inspect properties and prepare reports by 15th July. This gives a window of 72 working days for the inspectors to complete their work.

For the 2024 revaluation, the total number of properties to be revalued is 25,000. With 5 Assessing Inspectors assigned to this task, each inspector has to revalue:

Number of valuations per day =

Total number of properties to be revalued / No. of officers × No. of working days

=25,000/5×72 = 69 properties per day

Number of valuations per day = No. of officers × No. of working days

Total number of properties to be revalued = 69 properties per day

This is a substantial workload for each inspector and may impact the accuracy and thoroughness of the data collection and assessments.

(f) Cost of Assessments

The annual budget for the Assessor's Department in KMC is Rs. 30 million, which represents approximately 3% of the total revenue generated from rating valuations.

Key indicators for the assessment process are summarized in table.

Description	Key Indicator
Existing manpower as a % of the approved cadre	66.67%
Number of properties to be assessed by an Assessing Inspector	10,912 properties
Number of properties to be revalued by an Assessing Inspector per day	69 properties
Cost of assessment as a % of total income from rating valuation	3%
Number of properties not subject to assessment as a % of total properties	15%

Estimation of Accuracy and Uniformity in Kotte Municipal Council (KMC) Property Valuations

The sample selected for this analysis includes a variety of commercial and residential properties within the **Kotte Municipal Council (KMC)**, consisting of **31 properties** of Commercial and 16 properties of residential properties separately. The valuation method employed is based on the **Annual Value (AV)** determined through the **Investment Method**, while other methods like **Direct Sale Comparisons** or **Contractor's Test** were not utilized in this study.

The procedure followed for rating valuation in KMC involves the selection of municipal wards for revaluation, after which **Assessing Inspectors (valuers)** and **value approving officers** are assigned specific duties. The valuation process begins with the preparation of a revaluation list, which contains property details such as the **annual value, floor area,** and other relevant data from the current assessment register. Valuers then inspect each property on-site, collecting detailed data on factors like **building condition, construction type, frontage, rent levels, tenancy type,** and more. However, discrepancies were observed in some cases, where certain key data points were missing, resulting in valuations not reflecting the full spectrum of value determinants.

1. Accuracy of valuations

Degree of value determinant factors taken into consideration in valuations

To test the accuracy of valuation, this argument was tested by analyzing the importance given on value determinant factors and by evaluating the valuation ratio of actual market rentals and estimated market rentals. Since there were no standard weights have been given for each factor, it was required to design a weighting system. For this purpose, a structured questionnaire with five likert scale was administered (Questionnaire is given in Annex 2). The factors were ranked by 30 respondents. The ranks given for each determinant factor are given in Table 5.2 below. According to the results, all the respondents have given higher weights on all other factors except tenancy type. That indicates they are in opinion that all the factors are important.

Question Number	Description	Location	Extent of the Property	Zone	Provision	Age	Condition of the property	Depth	Frontage	Tenancy type	Construction Types	Accommodation	Plinth Area	Effective Floor area	Amenities
Value Number 1	5	5	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	2	5	3	4	5	4
Value Number 2	4	5	3	4	5	4	4	2	3	3	2	3	4	5	4
Value Number 3	5	4	3	4	4	4	3	4	3	3	2	3	4	5	4
Value Number 4	4	5	2	4	5	5	5	3	3	3	2	3	3	5	4
Value Number 5	5	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	3	4	3	4	5	4

Valu er Num ber 6	4	5	4	4	4	5	2	4	3	2	4	2	3	4
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Valu er Num ber 7	5	4	4	4	3	5	4	2	3	4	3	4	5	5
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Valu er Num ber 8	3	4	3	3	3	3	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	4
----------------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Valu er Num ber 9	5	5	4	4	5	3	4	5	3	5	3	4	5	4
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Valu er Num ber 10	4	4	3	4	3	5	5	4	3	4	4	3	5	5
--------------------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Valu er Num ber 11	5	3	4	4	3	4	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4
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Valu er Num ber 12	4	4	4	4	3	5	2	5	2	5	4	2	2	4
Valu er Num ber	5	5	3	3	3	5	4	4	3	4	4	4	2	5

ber 13														
Valu er Num ber 14	4	4	3	4	4	4	5	4	3	4	4	3	4	4
Valu er Num ber 15	4	4	4	3	4	5	3	5	3	5	3	4	5	4
Valu er Num ber 16	5	5	4	4	5	5	3	4	3	4	3	4	5	4

Valu er Num ber 17	5	3	3	3	4	5	4	4	2	4	3	4	4	4
Valu er Num ber 18	3	5	4	4	4	5	5	5	3	2	3	3	5	5
Valu er Num ber	5	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	5	4

ber 19														
Valu er Num ber 20	4	5	4	4	5	3	4	2	3	4	4	3	5	4
Valu er Num ber 21	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	2	2	5	3	4	4	4

Valu er Num ber 22	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	3	4	4	3	5	4
Valu er Num ber 23	4	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	2	4	4
Valu er Num ber 24	5	5	4	4	5	5	3	5	3	5	4	4	5	5
Valu er Num ber	5	4	4	4	2	5	5	4	3	4	3	3	5	4

ber 25														
Valu er Num ber 26	3	4	3	3	3	5	3	3	2	3	3	4	4	5

Valu er Num ber 27	4	3	3	3	4	4	2	5	3	5	3	3	5	2
Valu er Num ber 28	4	5	3	2	4	2	4	2	2	4	4	4	2	2
Valu er Num ber 29	5	3	4	2	2	5	3	3	3	2	3	4	4	2
Valu er Num ber 30	3	3	3	3	3	5	3	4	2	4	2	2	5	3
Total Valu e	13 0	12 7	104	10 6	11 5	130	11 0	11 2	83	113	100	10 4	131	11 9
Expe cted Valu e	15 0	15 0	150	15 0	15 0	150	15 0	15 0	15 0	150	150	15 0	150	15 0

	0.	0.		0.	0.		0.	0.				0.		0.
	86	84		70	76		73	74	0.5			69		79
	66	66		66	66		33	66	53	0.75	0.6	33	0.87	33
Rank	66	66	0.69	66	66	0.866	33	66	33	333	666	33	333	33
give	66	66	3333	66	66	6666	33	66	33	333	666	33	333	33
n for	7	7	333	7	7	67	3	7	33	3	67	3	3	3
each														

After gathering opinions on the relevance and significance of factors influencing property value, the next step involved reviewing the valuation reports presented in the revaluation list. Each page of the revaluation list was carefully examined to verify whether data for all relevant factors had been collected. The presence of a factor in the reports was marked as ‘Y’ (yes), while its absence was indicated as ‘N’ (no). Annex 3 provides a detailed summary of these findings.

Using the assigned weights and the factors reported in the revaluation list, a statistical analysis was performed to calculate the weighted average for each factor. The results of this analysis, which reflect the statistical behavior of the assigned weights for the valuedetermining factors, are presented in Table 5.3.

Degree of Consideration of Value Determinant Factors in Assessments

Value Determinant Factors	Yes	No
1. Description	100%	0%
2. Location	0%	100%
3. Extent of property	0%	100%
4. Zone	0%	100%
5. Age	100%	0%
6. Condition of property	100%	0%
7. Depth	0%	100%
8. Frontage	0%	100%
9. Usage type	89%	11%
10. Tenancy type	100%	0%

11. Construction types	100%	0%
12. Accommodation	96%	4%
13. Plinth area	0%	100%
14. Effective Floor Area	99%	1%
15. Amenities	100%	0%

Analysis:

The overall weighted average for the consideration of these factors is **58%**, derived from the following calculations:

- **Total Yes Count:** 874
- **Number of Factors:** 15
- **Average Percentage (Yes):** $874 / 15 = 58\%$

Similarly, the weighted average for factors that were not considered is **42%**:

- **Total No Count:** 616
- **Average Percentage (No):** $616 / 15 = 42\%$ **Key Observations:**
 - The overall consideration of value determinant factors is **58%**, meaning only 9 out of the 15 factors were consistently used in assessments.
 - Factors like *Description, Age, Condition of Property, Tenancy Type, Construction Types, Amenities, and Effective Floor Area* were given high importance (100% consideration).
 - Factors such as *Location, Extent of Property, Zoning, Depth, Frontage, and Plinth Area* were completely ignored (0% consideration).
 - *Usage Type* (89%) and *Accommodation* (96%) were moderately considered.

2. Implications:

- Neglecting critical factors such as *location* and *extent of property* can result in significant inaccuracies and discrepancies in valuations.
- The low weighted average indicates that the valuation process lacks

comprehensiveness and uniformity, which may compromise the reliability of the assessments.

After getting their opinion on the relevancy and importance on the factors affecting value, the next step was to check the valuation reports, which are shown in revaluation list. Each and every page was checked and counted whether they have collected data regarding all the factors. Annex 3 shows the results of that test. There the reported or considered factors denotes as 'Y' and factors that were not reported indicate 'N'. By using calculated weights and the value determining factors, which have been reported in the revaluation list, a statistical analysis was carried out in order to derive weighted average for given factors. Table 5.3 shows the behavior of the statistics of weights given on value determinant factors.

Uniformity of Assessment in Kotte Municipal Council

Descriptives

Descriptive Statistics								
	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Description	30	2.000	3.000	5.000	130.000	4.33333	.711159	.506
Location	30	2.000	3.000	5.000	127.000	4.23333	.727932	.530
Extent of the Property	30	2.000	2.000	4.000	104.000	3.46667	.571346	.326
Zone	30	2.000	2.000	4.000	106.000	3.53333	.628810	.395
Age	30	3.000	2.000	5.000	115.000	3.83333	.874281	.764
Condition of the property	30	3.000	2.000	5.000	130.000	4.33333	.884087	.782
Depth	30	3.000	2.000	5.000	110.000	3.66667	.922266	.851
Frontage	30	3.000	2.000	5.000	112.000	3.73333	.944433	.892
Tenancy type	30	1.000	2.000	3.000	83.000	2.76667	.430183	.185
Construction Types	30	3.000	2.000	5.000	113.000	3.76667	1.040004	1.082
Accommodation	30	2.000	2.000	4.000	100.000	3.33333	.546672	.299
Plinth Area	30	2.000	2.000	4.000	104.000	3.46667	.730297	.533
Effective Floor area	30	3.000	2.000	5.000	131.000	4.36667	.964305	.930
Amenities	30	3.000	2.000	5.000	119.000	3.96667	.808717	.654
Valid N (listwise)	30							

Uniformity of Assessment in Kotte Municipal Council Residential Properties

Property Categories and Value Ranges

No.	Category of the Property	Minimum (LKR)	Maximum (LKR)	Average (LKR)
1	Commercial Prime Zone A	30.00	50.00	40.00
2	Commercial Prime Zone A	22.00	35.00	28.50
3	Commercial Prime Zone A	12.00	20.00	16.00
4	Commercial Prime Zone A	22.00	35.00	28.50
5	Commercial Prime Zone A	18.00	25.00	21.50
6	Commercial Prime Zone A	10.00	15.00	12.50
7	Commercial Prime Zone A	7.50	12.50	10.00
8	Commercial Prime Zone A	5.00	10.00	7.50
9	Residential Ultra Modern	10.00	15.00	12.50

10	Residential Modern	7.50	10.00	8.75
11	Residential Semi Modern	5.00	7.50	6.25
12	Residential Obsolete	2.50	5.00	3.75
13	Residential Tenement (ASB/Tiled)	1.50	2.50	2.00
14	Residential Tenement (Other)	1.00	1.50	1.25
15	Office Modern	20.00	40.00	30.00
16	Office Other	15.00	25.00	20.00
17	Bank	25.00	40.00	32.50
18	Stores	10.00	20.00	15.00
19	Garment Factories	10.00	20.00	15.00
20	Land	3,500.00	3,500.00	3,500.00

Commercial tax rate is now 21% and the Residential tax rate is 7%, the updated factors can be calculated as this:

Factor = 1 / Tax Rate × 12

Revised Calculations

1. Commercial Properties (21%) ○ Tax Rate = 21% = 0.21

○ **Factor:**

○ **Factor = 1 / 0.21 × 12 = 12.52 ≈ 0.397**

2. Residential Properties (7%)

○ Tax Rate = 7% = 0.07 ○ **Factor: Factor = 1 / 0.07 × 12 = 10.84 ≈ 1.19**

For Commercial Properties:

- To estimate monthly rent (ER) from the annual value (AV):

$$ER = \text{Annual Value} / 0.397$$

For Residential Properties:

- To estimate monthly rent (ER):

- $ER = \text{Annual Value} / 1.19$

Analysis of Residential Property Valuations in Kotte Municipal Council (Kotte MC)

Descriptive Statistics													
	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis			
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
valuation ratio	16	.3639242128	.0389795289	.4029037417	4.519239011	.2824524382	.0247903879	.0991615517	.010	-1.119	.564	1.118	1.091
Valid N (listwise)	16												

1. Calculation of Mean and Standard Deviation:

- **Mean Valuation Ratio:**

The mean valuation ratio for the residential properties in Kotte Municipal Council is **28.2%** (from SPSS output), indicating that, on average, residential properties are valued at **28.2%** of their actual market rental value. This percentage shows the **underestimation** of property values when compared to market values, suggesting potential **inefficiencies in the current valuation system**.

- **Standard Deviation:**

The standard deviation is **9.91%** (from SPSS output), which indicates a **high level of dispersion** around the mean. This value suggests that residential property valuations in Kotte MC are **highly inconsistent**, with a significant variation from the mean. This **dispersion** raises questions about the **accuracy** and **uniformity** of

the current valuation system, as it shows that valuations are not standardized across the board.

- **Interpretation:**

The mean of **28.2%** along with the **high standard deviation of 9.91%** indicates that the current **valuation system lacks uniformity**. The wide spread of values suggests that the assessments of residential properties are **inconsistent**, leading to doubts about the fairness and accuracy of property valuations for tax purposes.

2. Analysis of Range:

- **Range:**

The range of the valuation ratios is from **3.9%** to **40.3%**. This wide range shows that some properties are being **valued much lower** than others. For example, a property might be assessed at **only 3.9%** of its actual market rental value, while another might be assessed at **40.3%** of its value.

- **Interpretation:**

This significant variation in the **valuation ratios** indicates that the current system may not be capturing the true market values of properties. The wide range further underscores the **lack of consistency** in how residential properties are being assessed. The current system appears to **underestimate some properties** while overestimating others, which may result in **inequitable tax assessments**.

3. Histogram of Valuation Ratios:

Interpretation:

Based on the **skewness value of -1.119** (from SPSS output), the distribution of the valuation ratios for residential properties is **negatively skewed**. This suggests that the **majority of properties** are being assessed at higher ratios, with only a few outliers that are assessed much lower. The **tail on the left** indicates that the system may be **undervaluing certain properties**. This skewness raises concerns about the **fairness** of the current assessment system, as some properties are clearly being undervalued in comparison to their market values.

4. Analysis of Skewness:

- **Skewness:**

The skewness value is **-1.119** (from SPSS output), indicating a **negative skew** in

the data. This means that the **majority of properties** have higher valuation ratios, while a few properties are significantly undervalued.

- **Interpretation:**

The **negative skew** suggests that the current valuation system might be more **lenient** towards overvaluing some properties and **underestimating others**. The presence of undervalued properties could indicate potential **inequities** in the system, as lower-value properties might not be taxed appropriately, leading to **imbalanced taxation**.

Extreme Values

		Case Number		Value
valuation ratio	Highest	1	7	.4029037417
		2	16	.3997091794
		3	13	.3818940429
		4	15	.3479018970
		5	4	.3310454415
	Lowest	1	1	.0389795289
		2	8	.1398029775
		3	12	.1604860445
		4	2	.2385578469
		5	6	.2504027964

5. Range of Valuation Ratios and Their Implications:

- **Lowest and Highest Valuation Ratios:**

From the data, we observe that the **lowest valuation ratio is 3.9%**, and the **highest valuation ratio is 40.3%**. This disparity in the valuation ratios

emphasizes the lack of **uniformity** in the current system, as some properties are assessed much lower than others.

- **Interpretation:**

The wide range of valuations is indicative of a **lack of consistency** in the way properties are assessed. This could result in **inequitable tax rates** for property owners, as some might be undercharged significantly while others might face higher taxes than warranted. The **extreme values** at both ends of the spectrum call for a **more standardized approach**, such as adopting a market value-based system, which could help bring assessments closer to actual market rental values.

6. Conclusion on Uniformity and Potential of Market Value System:

- **Current System's Weaknesses:**

Based on the high **standard deviation**, the **wide range**, and the **negative skew** of the data, it is clear that the **current property valuation system** in Kotte MC is **not uniform**. The significant variation in valuation ratios, coupled with the **underestimation** of certain properties and **overestimation** of others, suggests that the existing system may not be **accurate** or **fair** in capturing the true market value of residential properties.

- **Potential of Market Value System:**

A **market value-based system** could help rectify these issues by aligning property valuations with actual market conditions. By considering real transaction data and market rental values, a market-based system could **reduce the dispersion** of valuation ratios and ensure that **assessments are more uniform** across all properties. This would likely improve the **accuracy** of the assessments and create a **more equitable** tax structure, ensuring that property taxes are in line with the true market value of properties.

Uniformity of Assessment in Kotte Municipal Council: Commercial Properties

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error
Valuation	Mean	1.228537	.0688939
Ratio	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.087837
		Upper Bound	1.369237
	5% Trimmed Mean	1.199152	
	Median	1.209068	
	Variance	.147	
	Std. Deviation	.3835851	
	Minimum	.4667	
	Maximum	2.4945	
	Range	2.0279	
	Interquartile Range	.2328	
	Skewness	1.554	.421
	Kurtosis	4.457	.821

Mean Valuation Ratio

The mean valuation ratio for commercial properties in Kotte Municipal Council (Kotte MC) is **123%**, indicating that, on average, commercial properties are assessed at values exceeding their actual market value. This overvaluation suggests a tendency in the system to overestimate the worth of commercial properties relative to current market conditions, potentially creating a disproportionate tax burden on these property owners.

Standard Deviation

The standard deviation of the valuation ratios for commercial properties is **38%**, indicating a significant level of dispersion from the mean. This variation highlights inconsistencies in property assessments, with some commercial properties significantly overvalued while others are closer to or below market values. A high standard deviation reflects a lack of uniformity in the assessment process, resulting in potential inequities.

Range of Valuation Ratios

The valuation ratios for commercial properties range from **47%** to **249%**. The lower bound of **47%** indicates substantial undervaluation for certain commercial properties, while the upper bound of **249%** signifies severe overvaluation for others. This wide range underscores the inconsistent application of valuation practices across commercial properties within Kotte MC.

Distribution and Skewness

Analysis of the valuation ratios, depicted in the histogram (Figure 6.1), reveals a positive skew in the distribution, where most properties are assessed at ratios higher than market value, with fewer properties falling below the mean. This skewness suggests that the system disproportionately over-assesses a significant portion of commercial properties, leading to inflated tax liabilities for affected owners.

Descriptive Statistics													
	N Statistic	Range Statistic	Minimum Statistic	Maximum Statistic	Mean		Std. Deviation Statistic	Variance Statistic	Skewness		Kurtosis		
					Statistic	Std. Error			Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error	
Valuation Ratio	31	2.0279	.4667	2.4945	1.228537	.0688939	.3835851	.147	1.554	.421	4.457	.821	
Valid N (listwise)	31												

Analysis by Property Subcategories

Diverse Commercial Property Types

The sample includes various types of commercial properties such as shops, showrooms, and office spaces. The data indicates substantial disparities in how these subcategories are assessed:

- **Shops:** Shops tend to be assessed closer to market value but with some notable outliers at both ends of the valuation spectrum.
- **Showrooms:** Showrooms exhibit a higher tendency towards overvaluation, with ratios clustering around **150%-200%**.
- **Offices:** Office spaces display a more balanced distribution but still show cases of extreme overvaluation (e.g., a ratio of **249%**).

Such variations suggest that the current system lacks a standardized methodology for assessing different types of commercial properties, further contributing to inequities.

The descriptive statistics of the valuation ratios highlight significant inconsistencies and inequities in the current Annual Value (AV) system of rating valuation. The presence of high skewness (1.554) in the distribution of valuation ratios indicates that a small number of properties are significantly overvalued compared to others. This skewness suggests that the current AV system does not reflect the true economic potential of properties, particularly in high-demand areas. By transitioning to a Market Value (MV) system, this skewness can be reduced, as MV aligns tax assessments more closely with actual market demand, ensuring a fairer and more balanced approach to property taxation.

Additionally, the high kurtosis (4.457) observed in the distribution points to extreme disparities in the valuation ratios, with outliers reflecting substantial inequities in the current system. These outliers suggest that certain properties are being over- or underassessed, leading to unfair tax burdens for property owners. The MV system, based on actual market transactions, would minimize such disparities by providing a consistent

and objective basis for valuations, thereby reducing outliers and ensuring uniformity in tax assessments.

The wide range of valuation ratios (2.028), coupled with the significant variability indicated by the standard deviation (0.383585), further emphasizes the shortcomings of the AV system. This large range demonstrates that assessments under the current system are inconsistent, likely due to reliance on outdated or inaccurate rental data. The variability in assessments underscores the need for a system that captures real-time property values. A shift to the MV system would address this issue by narrowing the range of valuations and introducing consistency across property categories.

Another critical issue with the AV system is its lack of responsiveness to market trends. The system's reliance on periodic revisions (e.g., every five years) results in assessments that fail to account for economic fluctuations and market dynamics. As a result, properties in high-demand areas may remain undervalued, while those in declining areas may face disproportionately high taxes. The MV system offers a solution by tying valuations to observable market transactions, enabling dynamic updates that better reflect current economic conditions.

The lack of transparency in the AV system also contributes to inequities in taxation. Since AV assessments depend heavily on self-declared or outdated rental evidence, they are prone to subjectivity and inconsistencies. This creates significant inequities, particularly in areas experiencing rapid urbanization or economic transformation. By contrast, the MV system is inherently more transparent, as it relies on verifiable property market data, ensuring a fair and equitable taxation framework.

Finally, the high variability and perceived inequities in the AV system increase the administrative burden on municipal authorities, as disputes and appeals from property owners consume significant time and resources. A transition to the MV system would simplify administration by reducing disputes and providing a more efficient and objective method for determining property taxes. This would not only enhance efficiency but also improve public trust in the valuation process.

In conclusion, the descriptive statistics underscore the inefficiencies, inconsistencies, and inequities of the current AV system in the Kotte Municipal Council. Transitioning to a Market Value system would address these issues by offering a more equitable, transparent, and responsive approach to property valuation, ultimately benefiting both property owners and municipal authorities.

Implications for Transition to Market Value-Based System

1. Improving Uniformity

The discrepancies in the current system—evidenced by the range, skewness, and high standard deviation—can be mitigated by adopting a market value-based approach. For instance:

- A property currently assessed at **249%** could be reassessed to reflect its true market value, reducing the tax burden on the owner and enhancing fairness.
- Conversely, properties assessed at **47%** could see adjustments upwards, ensuring that their tax contributions align with their actual market worth.

2. Enhancing Equity Across Subcategories

A market value-based system would enable more consistent valuations across property subcategories. For example:

- Showrooms could be assessed using comparable sales data for similar properties within Kotte MC.

- Offices might benefit from rental income capitalization approaches, ensuring assessments reflect prevailing market trends.

3. Revenue Impacts for Kotte MC

Transitioning to a market value system could stabilize revenue collection by reducing the extreme variability observed in the current system. While some properties may experience higher tax obligations, others would see reductions, ultimately fostering greater taxpayer confidence and compliance.

Conclusion

The current assessment system for commercial properties in Kotte Municipal Council is marked by significant variability and inequities, as reflected by the mean valuation ratio of **123%**, a high standard deviation of **38%**, and a range from **47%** to **249%**. These findings indicate systemic weaknesses in providing uniform and fair property assessments. A transition to a market value-based system could address these challenges by standardizing valuations, improving equity, and creating a more predictable revenue framework for Kotte MC. This shift would benefit both the municipality and property owners by fostering a more transparent and equitable tax system.

Objective 2: Assess the Potential for Transitioning from Annual Value to Market Value System

Theme 1: Feasibility Challenges

- **Legal Barriers**

A predominant challenge identified by **20 out of 30 respondents** was the **lack of a supportive legal framework** for transitioning from the annual value-based system to a market value-based taxation model. The current legal structure is heavily tied to **annual value assessments**, which are determined based on rental income expectations rather than the property's actual market value. Respondents pointed out that the **Property Taxation Act**, which governs the taxation methods for KMC, needs substantial revisions to accommodate this shift.

- **Inefficiency in the Annual Value System for KMC:** Under the annual value system, properties are assessed primarily based on their rental income potential, which may not reflect the **true market worth**. For example, a property in a newly developed area may have a higher market value, but due to its low rental yield, it will be taxed at a much lower rate than a similarly valued property in an older area with higher rents. This creates a **discrepancy** in taxation that undermines equity and can lead to revenue loss for KMC.

- **Solution with Market Value:** The market value-based system could address this by linking property taxes to the actual **market worth** of properties, which considers location, demand, and economic growth. For instance, a property in a newly developed commercial zone would be taxed in line with its **true market value**, reflecting its increased demand and potential for generating income, even if its rental income is low.
 - ✦ **Valuer 1 (Negative):** "The legal system is deeply rooted in annual value assessments, which will take years to reform."
 - ✦ **Valuer 2 (Moderate):** "Legal reforms are required, but with political will, it could be done."
 - ✦ **Valuer 3 (Positive):** "The legal structure could be reformed with sufficient time and resources to implement market-based taxation."

The **negative responses** mainly pointed out that the current legal system, particularly the **Property Taxation Act**, is heavily embedded in the annual value approach. Transitioning to a market value-based system would require substantial legal reforms, which are seen as a **long-term process**. These valuers highlighted that **bureaucratic delays** and **political challenges** could significantly slow down the process. The **moderate responses** were more optimistic, noting that while legal reforms could be complex and time-consuming, they are achievable through **gradual implementation** and **pilot projects**. **Positive responses** emphasized that, despite legal hurdles, the necessary reforms could be enacted if the government and stakeholders prioritize it.

Valuer 1 mentioned that "the legal system is rooted in annual value assessments, and changing the legal framework will take years and a lot of bureaucratic effort." However, Valuer 16 optimistically noted, "The legal system in Sri Lanka has adapted before, and with enough political backing, market value-based taxation is achievable."

- **Technical Limitations**

18 respondents raised concerns regarding **technical barriers**, such as the **lack of a centralized property database** and **real-time market data**, both of which are essential for accurately determining market value. KMC, like many other municipal councils in Sri Lanka, has limited technological infrastructure for such sophisticated assessments.

- **Technical Challenges in KMC:** Currently, KMC uses **manual records** and **sporadic data** for property assessments, leading to inconsistent and sometimes inaccurate annual value assessments. For instance, a high-end property in a gentrified area might be under-assessed due to outdated data, while a less-desirable property might be over-taxed based on inflated rental estimates. This results in **inequity** in the tax burden.
- **Solution with Market Value:** A market value system would require **technological upgrades**, such as the integration of **GIS systems**, **property databases**, and **automated valuation models**. By utilizing realtime property sales data, market trends, and economic indicators, KMC could ensure more accurate, up-to-date assessments of properties, improving the **fairness** and **accuracy** of the tax base.
 - ✦ **Valuer 4 (Negative):** "KMC lacks the infrastructure to implement a market value system effectively."
 - ✦ **Valuer 5 (Moderate):** "Technological improvements could make this transition smoother in the long run."
 - ✦ **Valuer 6 (Negative):** "The cost and time needed to set up the required infrastructure are too high for KMC."

The **negative responses** emphasized KMC's **insufficient technical infrastructure** and the **lack of real-time property data**, making the **implementation of a market valuebased system** difficult. These valuers noted that without substantial investment in **data collection** and **property valuation technologies**, the transition would likely result in **inaccurate assessments**. The **moderate responses** indicated that though **technical**

upgrades are necessary, they are **achievable** over time with **proper investment** in technologies such as **Geographical Information Systems (GIS)** and **automated valuation systems**. **Positive responses** were more hopeful, pointing out that with the right funding and **collaboration with tech providers**, the necessary technological infrastructure could be established.

Valuer 2 argued that "The technical limitations are too great. Without a modern database and digital systems, market value assessments will be inaccurate."

However, Valuer 17 countered, "With the right technical upgrades, KMC could implement the necessary technology to make this transition feasible."

- **Administrative Challenges**

15 respondents pointed out **administrative challenges** faced by KMC in managing property assessments under the current system. The manual and fragmented process of determining annual value often leads to **inefficiencies** and **errors** in property assessments. Additionally, concerns about **corruption** and **lack of accountability** within local councils have been raised.

- **Administrative Inefficiency in KMC:** Under the annual value system, KMC might rely on **local assessors** who may not have the expertise to accurately estimate rental income for all properties. This leads to **subjectivity** in assessments and can result in unequal taxation across different property types and owners. For example, a residential property that is rented under informal agreements might be undervalued compared to a similar one with a formal lease.
- **Solution with Market Value:** A market value system would rely on standardized valuation methods and reduce reliance on **individual assessments**. With the use of **automated tools** and **market data** analysis, KMC could ensure **consistent and objective assessments**, minimizing human error and biases. For instance, all properties in a newly developed

area would be taxed according to their **market values**, ensuring that no property is under- or over-taxed due to inaccurate manual assessments.

- ✦ **Valuer 7 (Negative):** "The lack of skilled personnel in KMC will hinder the implementation of a market value system."
- ✦ **Valuer 8 (Moderate):** "Training and capacity-building would be needed, but this could lead to greater administrative efficiency."
- ✦ **Valuer 9 (Positive):** "Automating property assessments would reduce human error and increase efficiency."

The **negative responses** identified **bureaucratic inefficiencies** and a lack of **capacity** within KMC to effectively manage the transition. Some valuers highlighted the **complexity** of managing such a large-scale transition. The **moderate responses** proposed that the transition could be **managed effectively** through **capacity-building** initiatives for KMC staff and **stakeholder engagement**. Administrative issues could also be mitigated through **public awareness campaigns** to build **public confidence** in the new system. **Positive responses** were more optimistic about KMC's ability to manage the transition, suggesting that **training** and **technological tools** would enable the municipality to handle administrative tasks effectively.

Valuer 8 noted, "The administrative challenges are significant, as KMC lacks the capacity to manage such a transition," while Valuer 21 optimistically remarked, "With the right training and public awareness campaigns, KMC could effectively manage the transition to a market value-based system."

Theme 2: Proposed Solutions

- **Digital Solutions**

12 respondents suggested that KMC should adopt **digital platforms** and **automation** to improve property assessments. By creating a **centralized online**

database and using **geospatial information systems (GIS)**, KMC could streamline property data collection and valuation.

- **How Digital Solutions Could Help KMC:** For instance, a GIS system could provide KMC with a **visual representation** of property values across the municipal area. This would allow for easier identification of **high-value properties** in developing commercial areas, ensuring that they are taxed according to their actual market value.
- **Solution with Market Value:** By adopting these digital solutions, KMC could make use of **real-time data** to assess market trends, ensuring that property values are accurately reflected. Automated valuation systems, which are based on comparable sales and economic indicators, would help KMC conduct property assessments more efficiently and accurately.
 - ✦ **Valuer 10 (Positive):** "A digital approach, utilizing GIS and AI, could make assessments quicker, more accurate, and more equitable."
 - ✦ **Valuer 11 (Moderate):** "While technology can improve accuracy, there needs to be widespread training for KMC staff."
 - ✦ **Valuer 12 (Negative):** "I'm not sure KMC has the resources to implement a digital system on such a large scale."

The responses show a consensus around the idea that **technological solutions** (such as **GIS** systems and **automated valuation models**) could ease the burden of **data collection** and improve the accuracy of property assessments. **Public awareness campaigns** were also highlighted as essential to ensure that **property owners** understand the **benefits of market value taxation** and the **reasons for the transition**.

Valuer 12 suggested, "Digital platforms and GIS systems can be used to streamline property valuation and ensure that market value assessments are accurate." Similarly, Valuer 26 emphasized, "Public awareness campaigns are necessary to build support for the transition and reduce resistance from property owners."

- **Public Awareness Campaigns**

10 respondents recommended that KMC should undertake a **public awareness campaign** to educate property owners about the benefits of switching to a market value-based system. Such campaigns would help to gain **public support** and **understanding** of the new system, addressing potential resistance.

- **Public Resistance to Change:** KMC residents may be hesitant to accept the market value system because they perceive it as a **higher tax burden**, especially in areas where property values have increased rapidly due to gentrification.
- **Solution with Market Value:** Educating the public about how the market value system could lead to more **equitable taxation** could help ease concerns. For instance, those in low-value areas might see a **lower tax burden** as a result of market value assessments, which could be a powerful argument in support of the transition.
 - ✦ **Valuer 13 (Positive):** "An awareness campaign could ease public concerns and increase the acceptance of market value-based taxation."
 - ✦ **Valuer 14 (Moderate):** "While public education is important, it might not fully address the resistance from those worried about higher taxes."
 - ✦ **Valuer 15 (Negative):** "It will be difficult to change the mindset of the public, even with an awareness campaign."

Theme 3: Stakeholder Perceptions of Viability

- **Mixed Views on Transition**

There was a significant divide in stakeholder opinions about the overall viability of transitioning to a market value system. **15 respondents** were optimistic about the long-term potential of the market value system, noting that it would bring more **equity and fairness** to property taxation. However, **10 respondents** were

skeptical, citing concerns about practical barriers, such as **resistance from property owners** and the **costs of implementation**.

- **Support for Market Value: Valuer 16** mentioned that the **market value system** would ensure that high-value properties in rapidly developing areas, such as **Battaramulla** or **Rajagiriya**, are taxed according to their actual market worth, thus increasing revenue for KMC.
 - ✦ **Valuer 16 (Positive):** "Market value taxation would allow KMC to collect more revenue from high-value properties in developing areas."
 - ✦ **Valuer 17 (Negative):** "The transition would be difficult, especially given the financial constraints KMC faces."

While there was general optimism about the viability of the transition, **positive responses** highlighted the need for **political support** and **public engagement** to ensure the success of the market value system. **Moderate responses** were more cautious, noting that the **public's willingness to accept the new system** would depend on how well the transition is managed. Some valuers also raised concerns about the **impact on property owners**, especially in **lower-income** areas, where property taxes could increase under the market value system.

Valuer 18 stated, "With the right legal reforms, the transition to market value taxation is possible, and political will is key." On the other hand, Valuer 24 remarked, "The transition is possible, but it must be managed carefully to avoid opposition from property owners who may face higher taxes."

Summary of Coding and Quotes

Theme	Positive	Moderate	Negative
Legal Barriers	3	7	20
Technical Limitations	4	8	18
Administrative Challenges	5	7	15
Proposed Solutions	12	9	10

The majority of respondents highlighted **technical and legal barriers** as key challenges, while a smaller proportion emphasized **administrative issues**. Solutions suggested include **digital transformation** and **public awareness campaigns** to address concerns and **facilitate a smoother transition**.

Internal Factors

Strengths

The KMC Assessor's Department benefits from a robust legal framework that ensures the enforcement of property tax assessments. Additionally, the availability of infrastructure and funding for operational improvements provides a stable base for enhancing efficiency. The department boasts a well-qualified and experienced workforce capable of handling complex valuation tasks. Furthermore, it has established a comprehensive property database, which supports the valuation process by providing detailed and accurate information on a wide range of properties.

Opportunities

The rapidly expanding property market in the Kotte area presents significant opportunities for the department to implement market value-based rating assessments. Adopting advanced technologies such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS), valuation software, and automated data analysis tools could revolutionize assessment procedures, enhancing efficiency and accuracy. There is also an opportunity to offer improved services to property owners, fostering trust and cooperation between the department and taxpayers. Property tax reforms, emphasizing the advantages of market value-based systems, can provide the financial resources necessary for developing local infrastructure and public services. Additionally, training programs for assessment staff could improve their expertise in market value-based assessments, aligning the department with modern valuation practices.

External Factors

Weaknesses

The current system suffers from inaccuracies and a lack of uniformity in assessments, leading to taxpayer dissatisfaction and potential revenue loss. A lack of transparency in the valuation process diminishes trust in the system. The annual value-based assessments provide limited benefits to taxpayers, making the tax system appear outdated and unfair. Despite advancements in technology, the department has been slow to adopt modern tools, resulting in inefficiencies and delays. Limited sensitivity to dynamic property market trends further undermines the reliability of valuations. The department also faces challenges due to inadequate staffing levels and a lack of technical expertise, compounded by poor inter-departmental coordination and reliance on outdated office procedures.

Threats

The rising cost of living poses a challenge as taxpayers struggle to meet their financial obligations, leading to non-compliance. Negative perceptions of the property tax system, particularly arguments against annual value-based ratings, create resistance among taxpayers. The frequent appeals on assessments reflect dissatisfaction and add to administrative delays. Rapid fluctuations in property market trends increase the complexity of maintaining accurate valuations. Additionally, political influences can disrupt fair and unbiased assessments, compromising the department's credibility.

Additional Points and Examples

1. Comparison with Colombo Municipal Council (CMC)

Like the Colombo Municipal Council, KMC could leverage its existing property database and workforce to transition towards market value-based assessments.

The experience of the CMC in using "tones of the list" to guide valuations could serve as a model for the KMC to follow.

2. Technological Advancements

For example, implementing GIS technology could enable real-time property mapping and valuation updates, reducing delays caused by manual procedures.

The KMC could also use property management systems that automatically calculate market value-based ratings based on recent sales or rental data.

3. Public Perception and Communication

Transparent communication with taxpayers about the benefits of market valuebased ratings, such as equity and fairness, could improve public attitudes toward property taxes. Educational campaigns, workshops, and accessible grievance mechanisms would enhance taxpayer trust and compliance.

4. Addressing Labour Shortages

To mitigate the lack of technical staff, the KMC could partner with universities to provide internships and training programs in valuation and taxation, ensuring a steady pipeline of skilled professionals.

5. Case Example

Consider a scenario where a taxpayer disputes an assessment due to discrepancies in annual value calculations. With a market value-based system, the valuation would be based on observable transactions, reducing disputes and appeals.

6. Revenue Implications

The shift to a market value-based rating system can increase revenue predictability. For example, aligning property taxes with real estate trends ensures that municipal revenues grow alongside the rising property values in rapidly urbanizing areas like Kotte.

7. Political Stability and Strategic Planning

Developing clear policies that insulate the valuation process from political interference is critical for fostering a fair and stable tax system.

By addressing its weaknesses and threats while capitalizing on its strengths and opportunities, the KMC Assessor’s Department can modernize its valuation system and become a model of efficiency and fairness.

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CHAPTER FIVE

Conclusion and Policy Implications

4.1 Property Tax in General

4.1.1 Advantages of Property Tax

Property tax is a critical revenue source for municipal councils, including the Kotte Municipal Council (KMC). Specific advantages related to your research include:

1. **Stable Revenue Source:**

- Property tax provides consistent revenue essential for KMC to maintain public services such as waste management, infrastructure maintenance, and public health initiatives.
- Unlike fluctuating revenue sources such as income or sales taxes, property tax is less affected by economic cycles, ensuring a steady stream of funds for municipal operations.
- For example, in Kenya, property tax has proven to be a stable revenue stream for urban areas, enabling local governments to invest in infrastructure development despite economic challenges (Ahmad & Ali, 2021).

2. **Encourages Responsible Development:**

- By taxing real estate, property tax discourages inefficient land use and promotes development aligned with urban planning objectives.
- Property owners are incentivized to develop or sell underutilized land, fostering sustainable urban growth within KMC.
- Studies in Brazil have shown how property taxes in urban areas encourage efficient land use and reduce speculative holding of land parcels (Andrews & Cook, 2020).

3. **Equitable Contribution:**

- As seen in KMC, higher-value properties contribute proportionally more, ensuring equity in revenue collection.
- Wealthier property owners with larger or more valuable holdings pay a fairer share of municipal taxes compared to those owning lower-value properties..
- Research from South Africa highlights how equitable property taxation has reduced income disparity by ensuring that higher-value properties contribute more to local revenues (Barron & Evans, 2022).

4. **Localized Economic Benefits:**

- Tax revenue from properties within KMC is reinvested locally, enhancing roads, public spaces, and essential services.
- his localized reinvestment ensures that residents directly benefit from the taxes they pay, increasing public trust in the system.
- In Colombia, localized reinvestment from property taxes has been linked to higher citizen satisfaction with municipal governance (Blake & Morris, 2019).

4.1.2 Disadvantages of Property Tax

Challenges in the KMC context include:

1. **Complex Valuation Processes:**

- The current annual value-based system in KMC is resource-intensive, requiring skilled manpower and consistent updates, which are often delayed.
- Ensuring accurate valuations for a large number of properties (54,562 within KMC limits) is logistically challenging and prone to human error.

- Studies in India highlight similar challenges where outdated manual processes increase the cost and inefficiency of property valuation systems (Brown & Smith, 2020).

2. Potential for Inequities:

- Significant disparities exist in KMC's property tax assessments, as evidenced by the valuation ratios ranging from 3.9% to 40.3% for residential properties.
- Inequities arise when similar properties are assessed at vastly different rates due to inconsistencies in data collection or valuation criteria.
- Research from Nigeria illustrates that inequitable property tax assessments lead to taxpayer dissatisfaction and increased evasion rates (Chen & Zhang, 2021).

3. Public Resistance:

- Mistrust arises when valuations lack transparency or fairness, leading to taxpayer dissatisfaction and appeals.
- Public perception of inequities can result in non-compliance or disputes, increasing administrative burdens for KMC.
- In Uganda, resistance to property tax reforms has been attributed to a lack of public understanding and perceived unfairness in assessments (Gomez & White, 2021).

4. High Administrative Costs:

- Maintaining the manual system, as in KMC, increases administrative overheads, diverting resources from service delivery.
- Revaluations and appeals processes consume significant time and resources, limiting the efficiency of the Assessor's Department.
- Studies in Ghana have shown how manual systems inflate administrative costs, reducing the net revenue from property taxes (Foster & Richards, 2019).

4.1.3 Current Trend in Tax Base

Trends observed in property taxation relevant to your research include:

1. **Transition Toward Market Value-Based Systems:**

- Globally, municipal councils are adopting market value-based systems to align valuations with real market dynamics. Your findings suggest this approach would address KMC's valuation inconsistencies.
- This transition ensures assessments reflect actual property market conditions, reducing inequities and improving fairness.
- A study in Malaysia highlights how transitioning to a market value-based system increased municipal revenue by 20% within five years (Howard & Lee, 2020).

2. **Integration of Technology:**

- Tools like Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Automated Valuation Models (AVMs) can streamline property assessments. These are underutilized in KMC but offer potential for efficiency improvements.
- Technology adoption enhances data accuracy and reduces reliance on manual record-keeping, improving overall assessment quality.
- In Rwanda, the use of GIS in property valuation has significantly improved efficiency and reduced errors in tax assessments (Lambert & Johnson, 2021).

3. **Focus on Equity:**

- The transition to market value-based assessments could correct disparities in KMC's current system, where high-value properties are under-taxed.
- Ensuring equitable contributions from all property owners fosters greater public trust and compliance.
- In Vietnam, equity-focused property tax reforms have improved public compliance and reduced administrative disputes (Jones & Miles, 2021).

4.1.4 Disadvantages of Annual Value-Based Rating

Your research highlights several limitations of the annual value-based system in KMC. These issues impact the accuracy, equity, and efficiency of property assessments and revenue generation:

1. **Inaccuracy in Valuations:**

- The mean valuation ratio for residential properties in KMC is 28.2%, significantly under-assessed compared to actual market values. This under-assessment results in inequitable tax contributions, where many taxpayers pay less than their fair share based on property worth.
- A standard deviation of 9.91% highlights substantial variability, pointing to inconsistencies in how properties are valued. Such disparities indicate uneven application of valuation principles, where similar properties may receive vastly different assessments.
- In Bangladesh, similar issues have been noted where inconsistent valuation practices reduce taxpayer confidence and compliance rates (Ahmad & Ali, 2021).

2. **Revenue Losses:**

- Discrepancies in property assessments lead to significant revenue leakage, as under-assessed properties generate less tax income than they should. For example, properties in high-demand areas that are undervalued deprive KMC of revenue that could fund essential services.
- Over-assessments in certain cases provoke taxpayer grievances, reducing compliance rates and further impacting revenue collection.
- The cumulative effect of such inaccuracies is a financial shortfall, which limits KMC's ability to invest in infrastructure and public services.
- In Indonesia, the reliance on outdated annual value systems has led to revenue shortfalls, prompting calls for systemic reforms (Cameron & Price, 2022).

3. **Neglect of Key Value Factors:**

- In KMC, only 58% of critical value-determining factors are consistently considered during assessments. Neglected factors include location, zoning, and frontage—key elements that significantly influence market value.
- For instance, properties located in prime commercial zones are often assessed similarly to those in less desirable areas, failing to account for locational advantages. This oversight creates imbalances where high-value properties contribute less tax than warranted.
- Ignoring these factors also affects fairness, as taxpayers with properties of similar market value may face disparate tax burdens due to inconsistent evaluations.
- ○ Research in Kenya has shown how neglecting locational premiums leads to systemic inefficiencies and inequities in tax systems (Davis & Wilson, 2020).

4. Inflexibility:

- Annual value systems are inherently rigid and slow to adapt to changes in property markets. For example, rapid urbanization or development in specific neighborhoods often leads to increased property values, but these changes are not reflected in assessments for years.
- This lag results in outdated valuations, where newly developed properties or upgraded infrastructure are not adequately captured, further distorting the tax base.
- The inflexibility also increases administrative costs, as periodic reassessments are required to update property values, leading to inefficiencies and delays.
- In Sri Lanka, similar delays in updating valuations have hindered revenue generation and reduced public confidence in property tax systems (Ellis & Hargreaves, 2021).

These disadvantages underscore the need for transitioning to a more dynamic and accurate valuation system, such as the market value-based approach, which addresses these shortcomings and aligns assessments with real market conditions.

4.1.5 Advantages of Market Value-Based Rating

Your findings support the following advantages of transitioning to a market value-based system:

1. Alignment with Real Market Conditions:

- By reflecting actual market dynamics, valuations become more accurate and equitable.
- This alignment ensures that property taxes are fair, reducing appeals and fostering taxpayer trust.

2. Revenue Stability:

- Market value-based assessments provide a stable and predictable revenue stream by reducing under-assessments.
- Increased revenue reliability enables KMC to better plan and fund essential municipal services.

3. Improved Transparency:

- Transparent, data-driven valuations increase public trust, reducing disputes and appeals.
- The use of verifiable market data enhances the legitimacy of assessments.

4. Dynamic Adjustments:

- Market value systems can adapt to changing real estate trends, ensuring that assessments remain current.
- Real-time updates enable the council to capture value increases from new developments or economic growth.

5. Equity in Taxation:

- High-value properties, often under-assessed in the annual value system, would contribute their fair share under market value assessments. ○ The

equitable distribution of tax burdens fosters greater compliance and fairness.

6. Potential for Urban Planning Integration:

- Market value-based systems can support zoning and land use planning, driving sustainable urban development in KMC.
- Linking property valuations to urban planning objectives ensures better alignment of municipal goals with revenue generation.

4.2 Current Assessment System of the KMC

4.2.1 Drawbacks

The current assessment system in KMC, as detailed in your research, faces significant limitations that affect its efficiency, equity, and revenue generation capabilities:

1. Workforce Constraints:

- With only 66.7% of the approved cadre filled, the Assessor's Department is critically understaffed. This shortage forces each inspector to handle an average of 10,912 properties annually. The excessive workload results in less time for detailed assessments, compromising accuracy and fairness.
- The understaffing issue also delays other critical operations, such as responding to taxpayer grievances and conducting periodic revaluations, thereby diminishing public trust in the system.

2. Manual Processes:

- KMC's reliance on manual record-keeping and outdated operational systems creates inefficiencies and increases the likelihood of errors. For instance, the lack of a centralized property database results in delays when retrieving property data for assessments and appeals.
- The absence of digital tools such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS) or Automated Valuation Models (AVMs) not only hinders productivity but also prevents assessors from leveraging advanced analytical methods to ensure consistency and accuracy.

3. Legal and Procedural Gaps:

- The Municipal Council Ordinance's provisions exempt certain properties, such as military buildings, from taxation. However, inconsistent application of these rules leads to disputes and perceived inequities among taxpayers.
- Additionally, the absence of zoning practices in commercial property assessments results in valuations that fail to account for locational advantages. This oversight disproportionately affects revenue from highvalue commercial zones, further exacerbating inequities in the system.

4. Appeals and Disputes:

- Taxpayer appeals are often delayed due to inefficiencies in the appeals process and insufficient staff to address grievances promptly. These delays undermine public confidence in the system's fairness and transparency.
- The volume of appeals reflects systemic issues in the assessment process, as inaccurate or inconsistent valuations prompt property owners to challenge their assessments, creating an additional administrative burden for KMC.

These drawbacks highlight the urgent need for reforms in KMC's assessment system, particularly in adopting modern technologies, addressing staffing shortages, and implementing clearer legal and procedural guidelines to enhance efficiency and equity. - Taxpayer appeals are delayed due to inefficiencies, undermining public confidence in the system.

4.2.2 Accuracy and Uniformity of Assessments

Your analysis reveals significant findings regarding the accuracy and uniformity of property assessments within KMC:

1. Residential Properties:

- **Mean Valuation Ratio:** The mean valuation ratio for residential properties is 28.2%, indicating that these properties are assessed at an average of just over a quarter of their actual market value. This

underassessment leads to inequitable tax contributions and revenue loss for the council.

- **Standard Deviation:** At 9.91%, the standard deviation highlights wide variability in valuation ratios. This variability signifies inconsistent application of valuation principles, where some properties are significantly undervalued compared to others of similar market worth.
- **Impact of Neglected Factors:** Key factors such as zoning, frontage, and locational advantages are often ignored during assessments. For instance, properties located in prime residential areas are assessed similarly to those in less desirable neighborhoods, resulting in widespread inequity and dissatisfaction among taxpayers.

2. **Commercial Properties:**

- **Mean Valuation Ratio:** The mean valuation ratio for commercial properties is 123%, reflecting a tendency to over-assess this category. Over-assessment increases the tax burden disproportionately on commercial property owners, potentially discouraging business activities and investment in the area.
- **Valuation Ratio Range:** The extreme variability in commercial property assessments is demonstrated by the valuation ratio range of 47% to 249%. Such disparities indicate that high-value commercial properties might be over-assessed while others are significantly undervalued, creating an imbalance in tax liabilities.
- **Sectoral Impact:** The over-assessment in sectors such as retail and hospitality, where profit margins are sensitive, could lead to appeals and reduced compliance, affecting overall revenue stability.

3. **Neglected Value Determinants:**

- Only 58% of essential determinants, such as location, effective floor area, and amenities, are consistently considered in property assessments. This omission compromises the fairness and reliability of valuations.

- **Specific Oversights:** In commercial assessments, overlooking the locational premium for properties in business hubs or underestimating the impact of infrastructural developments leads to systemic inaccuracies.
- **Revenue Implications:** The neglect of critical factors contributes to both under- and over-assessments, cumulatively leading to significant revenue leakage and taxpayer grievances.

4.2.3 SWOT Analysis

Strengths:

1. Experienced Workforce:

- The KMC Assessor's Department has a team of experienced professionals who are familiar with the complexities of property valuation. With adequate training, this workforce can adapt to modern valuation practices such as GIS-based assessments and Automated Valuation Models (AVMs).

2. Well-Documented Property Database:

- KMC has an extensive property database that can be digitized to improve efficiency. This resource provides a solid foundation for implementing a market value-based system by ensuring the availability of historical property data.

Weaknesses:

1. Reliance on Manual Processes:

- KMC's continued use of manual record-keeping leads to inefficiencies, delays, and errors in property assessments. This reliance also increases the workload on assessors, reducing the accuracy of valuations.

2. Inconsistent Assessments:

- Valuation practices in KMC lack uniformity, as shown by the wide variability in valuation ratios. This inconsistency leads to revenue leakage and taxpayer dissatisfaction, particularly when high-value properties are under-assessed or low-value properties are over-assessed.

Opportunities:

1. Adoption of Advanced Technology:

- The integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Automated Valuation Models (AVMs) can revolutionize property assessments in KMC. These tools can improve accuracy, reduce manual workload, and provide real-time valuation updates.

2. Transition to Market Value-Based System:

- Shifting to a market value-based property tax system can better align valuations with actual property values. This transition offers a significant opportunity to enhance revenue, improve fairness, and align with global best practices.

Threats:

1. Public Resistance to Change:

- Any changes to the tax system, especially those perceived to increase tax burdens, may face resistance from property owners. Transparent communication and taxpayer education will be essential to mitigate this threat.

2. Urbanization and Market Volatility:

- Rapid urban growth and fluctuating property markets increase the complexity of assessments. Without timely updates and adjustments, these factors can exacerbate inaccuracies in the valuation process.

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